

A REVIEW OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT ON TEXTURIZATION OF
SILICON SOLAR CELLS

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ULASAN BERKENAAN PENYELIDIKAN DAN PEMBANGUNAN KE ATAS
PENGTEKSTURAN SEL SURIA SILIKON

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DISERTASI YANG DIKEMUKAKAN UNTUK MEMENUHI SEBAHAGIAN
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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the writing in this dissertation is my own except for quotations and summaries which have been duly acknowledged.

7 July 2015

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P76871

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All praise is due to Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful; all belong to Him alone the treasures of wisdom and knowledge, All-Knowing and the Most Wise. May blessing of Allah and peace upon Prophet Muhammad; a truthful messenger and as a mercy to the entire world. Thanks to Allah; this dissertation far from possible and cannot be done by my own self, unless with His bestowed inspiration, strength and perseverance.

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ABSTRACT

A considerable amount of incident light escaped from silicon solar cell from the front surface which reduces the overall energy conversion. Texturization; a process of producing desired unevenness in surface of solar cell is a one of solution to the problem. Front surface texture reduces the cell reflectivity and contributes to more photocurrent generation in active material. The literatures on research and development (R&D) aspects in silicon solar cell texturization are reviewed in the present study based on various published articles. There were five R&D aspects identified; they are the understanding of the mechanism of optical losses reduction, methods of texturization, desired texture feature, side effect of texturization, and its compatibility with other optical enhancement is for crystal silicon cell which fairly elaborated. The textured front silicon surface by physical or chemical method improves quantum efficiency of cell due to overall higher light absorption in visible range, especially long wavelength because of trapping mechanism. Texture feature in size range 0.1–10 μm with high homogeneity, uniformity, and near 100% coverage gives the best cell performance. Flat silicon after ingot sawing have reflectivity more than 35%; less than 10% reflectivity can be expected for textured silicon and as low as 2–3% after anti reflection coating is being applied. Front surface texture not only associated with minimization of optical losses but at same time affecting the carrier and electrical losses in negative way thus thoroughly discussed. If not treated properly, the increase in surface area decreases the carrier lifetime and increase series resistance. Light trapping in thin film cell could not differ much except the texture taken by the silicon after deposited on textured transparent conducting oxide, or textured metal back contact which depends on the cell configuration. The improvement of light trapping itself not likely can break the efficiency limit 25% but also need to solve the major problem in carrier and electrical losses in cell.

ABSTRAK

Sebahagian dari jumlah cahaya tuju lesap dari sel suria silikon melalui permukaan hadapan yang mana mengurangkan kecekapan penukaran tenaga keseluruhannya. Pengteksturan; proses menghasilkan permukaan tidak rata yang dikehendaki adalah salah satu penyelesaian kepada permasalahan. Tekstur permukaan hadapan mengurangkan pantulan sel dan menyumbang kepada lebih penghasilan foto-arus di dalam bahan aktif. Penulisan berkenaan aspek penyelidikan and pembangunan (R&D) pengteksturan sel suria silikon diulas di dalam kajian ini berdasarkan pelbagai artikel yang telah diterbitkan. Terdapat lima aspek R&D dikenalpasti; mereka adalah pemahaman tentang mekanisma pengurangan kehilangan optic, kaedah pengteksturan, ciri tekstur yang dikehendaki, kesan buruk pengteksturan, dan kesesuaiannya dengan penambahbaikan optic yang lain untuk sel suria silikon yang mana secara baiknya dihuraikan. Permukaan silikon yang telah ditekstur dari kaedah fizikal atau kimia membaiki kecekapan kuantum sel kerana penyerapan cahaya yang lebih tinggi di dalam julat cahaya nampak secara keseluruhannya, terutama jarak gelombang panjang oleh mekanisma pemerangkapan. Ciri tekstur bersaiz dalam julat 0.1–10 μ m dengan kemohogenan, keseragaman yang tinggi, dan hampir 100% liputan memberikan prestasi sel yang terbaik. Silikon rata selepas penggergajian jongkong mempunyai pantulan lebih 35%; pantulan kurang dari 10% boleh dijangka untuk silikon yang telah ditekstur dan serendah 2–3% selepas salutan anti pantulan dikenakan. Tekstur permukaan hadapan tidak hanya berkait dengan pengurangan kehilangan optic tetapi pada masa yang sama memberi kesan kepada kehilangan pembawa dan elektrik dari sudut yang negatif dan telah dibincangkan secara mendalam. Jika tidak dirawat secara berhemah, peningkatan luas permukaan mengurangkan jangka hayat pembawa dan meningkatkan rintangan sesiri. Pemerangkapan cahaya dalam sel filem nipis tidak jauh bezanya kecuali tesktur diambil oleh silikon selepas diendapkan atas oksida lutsinar pengalir atau sentuhan logam belakang yang telah ditekstur, yang mana bergantung pada konfigurasi sel. Penambahbaikan pemerangkapan cahaya sahaja seolah tidak dapat memecahkan had kecekapan 25% tetapi memerlukan penyelesaian kepada masalah besar dalam kehilangan pembawa dan elektrik dalam sel.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Renewable energy is a broad topic that attracts interest from many parties such as politician, economist and not to mention also academician. The reason lies in the demand of energy which keeps increasing from year to year and most of countries expected to face the dilemma of energy consumption. Major contributor of energy nowadays still comes from fossil fuel in which powering the electricity generation station, transportations, and applications which is appropriate. According to statistics from an oil company BP (2013), total world energy consumption for 2013 is nearly 13,000 million tons oil consumption in equivalent, noticeable increased in value if compared to previous baseline which is 9,300 and 8,100 million tons in year 2000 and 1990 respectively. In case of Malaysia which is a developing country which having estimated GDP of 10,538 USD per capita at 2013, depended on fossil fuel to generate electricity is significant. It is predicted to have around 82 % electrical generation comes from the fossil fuel in 2015 (Mekhilef et al. 2014).

The increase in attention given toward national energy supply capability plus the global warming and environmental issues consideration, photovoltaic technology received enough attention as one of widespread approach to a low carbon emission in energy production. Solar energy is renewable, sustainable and clean energy which sourced from the sun, one of good example of how renewable energy stand competitiveness with non-renewable energy. Make use of this energy help mankind to be less dependent on non-renewable energy source, cope with increasing population energy demand, and also reduce carbon footprint for every energy generation. As time

flows, technology for this area become more mature and make possible for further cost reduction in every Watt Peak (W_p) to encourage public involvement due to its affordability.

According to a report by Fraunhofer ISE (2014), silicon based solar cell dominate the major portion contribution in photovoltaic section with 90 percent total production in 2013. The remaining 10 percent is contribution from another type of solar cell which is thin film based which have their own advantages such as mostly build from cheap organic material, thin and flexible but exceptional in lower efficiency compared to the silicon based solar cell. The abundance of starting material for silicon processing, considerable high energy conversion efficiency and also proven longevity ensure the silicon cell as the top choice for small and massive scale application. One of noticeable massive application of photovoltaic technology beside the typical solar farm would be their installment on industrial and government building, promoted by the launch of the Malaysia Building Integrated Photovoltaic (MBIPV) project. This however need at minimum six to seven years of continuous generation and accounted in electricity bills before benefits of this technology being justified in term of cost analysis (Mekhilef et al. 2014). For the silicon based solar cell, they more likely able to survive within this period with minimum deterioration in power generation compared with non-silicon based.

Solar cell could be enhanced their performance by increase their photogeneration while at the same time reduce the electrical loss in the cell and glassed module. In this dissertation, one of key point in improving the efficiency was highlighted to lead future research and development on this area; it is by texturization. The texturization of silicon is a additional step in cell fabrication to enhance the overall performance characteristic of solar cell. Texturization in general understanding is a process of damaging the surface of silicon to obtain certain morphology. The reason because of uneven surface simply captures the incident light more effectively thus more of them can be converted into electrical energy. More details on fundamental knowledge and background information about silicon solar cell and texturization later can be found in next chapter.

1.2 PROJECT RATIONALE

This research project is relevant because global research and development work on silicon solar cell is still active because of promising efficiency of silicon as active material in solar cell. As the textured morphology of the silicon widely accepted by researcher and manufacturer to improve the performance of solar cell, the number of articles in this field roses significantly. A work in compilation, interpretation and detailed discussion on available literature is quite necessary in order to provide a guide for more potential research for newcomers, professional, and consultancy.

1.3 OBJECTIVE

The objectives of this research project are to:

- i. Gather the information from various literature regarding the research and development on texturization of silicon solar cell.
- ii. Compile all experimental data and information from literatures for a complete understanding and comparison with data interpretation and synthesis.
- iii. Provide the technical writing to be assessed in form of dissertation and a publishable review article.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of study in this work has been defined as follows:

- i. Target 100 publications to be reviewed; source diversified including low impact factor journal and paper in conference/proceeding. However, 40-50% (major portion) reserved for journal with impact factor 3 and higher, 20-30% for journal in impact factor 1-3, and the rest for low/no impact factor. This is to ensure broad study and search field. Recent article later than year 2000 is given priority to ensure quality of presentation.
- ii. All type of article to be accepted; review, experimental, theoretical and simulation research.

1.5 DISSERTATION OUTLINE

This dissertation consists of several main components in order to successfully deliver the output of study. The first chapter is about the introduction to the dissertation, as currently discussed. The second chapter is about research methodology. In this chapter, research questions that being generated by the author will be provided and the writing, argument and explanation of main chapter in this dissertation will about answering all these questions. Flow chart and Gantt chart for this research project also will be presented and in additional to that, knowledge maps which indicating the contribution of this dissertation in body of knowledge will be provided.

The early of third chapter is for refreshment in fundamental knowledge and working principal of silicon solar cell, then into the introduction of the need of surface texture in solar cell. The fourth chapter is on discussion and detailed review of the literatures. Every article transformed into simplified writing to answer the research question and provide a rich content reading. In this section also, if necessary, some illustrations from original research article will be bring along with the writing in order to help content being elaborated in proper manner. The conclusion will be reserved in chapter five. In this chapter, all the related findings in previous chapter summarized, clustered and the essence of work is pinned out. This section also contains some recommendation that should contribute to this field of study and any personnel which related.

CHAPTER II

METHODOLOGY

2.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The methodology of this dissertation was designed in such systematic way collecting the information and data to answer the research questions. During early stage of the project, questions were generated; they are:

- i. Why texturing is important and how it will contribute in enhancing the performance characteristics and the efficiency of solar cell?
- ii. What are factors determine the optical loss in typical solar cell?
- iii. How to produce the textured silicon surface and what is achievable texture?
- iv. Explain basic understanding about physical and chemical texturization.
- v. Which texturing method is most common and cost effective?
- vi. What are the influences of the size of textured micro/nano structure?
- vii. What is effect of initial silicon surface condition prior to texturization?
- viii. What kind of pre and post-treatment that might necessary to be implemented along with the silicon texturization?
- ix. For both monocrytalline and multicrystalline, how the crystal orientations of silicon effect the texturization?
- x. Differentiate the concept of texturization in conventional silicon and thin film silicon solar cell.
- xi. How the textured surface might negatively affect the cell fabrication?
- xii. Does the different silicon texture morphology result the different final effect or performance parameter on the completed fabricated cell?

2.2 RESEACRH ACTIVITIES

There are five stages of work that need to be carried out in order to successfully answering the questions and make the compilation of this dissertation possible; they are collection of literatures, selection of relevant literatures, review of literatures, information synthesize and interpretation, and lastly report writing and submission.

2.2.1 Collection of Literatures

The first stage is collection of research articles which relate with the topic. Reading material mostly articles in journals and might include some paper from proceedings that made possible by accessing via online library.

2.2.2 Selection of Relevant Literatures

After pools of electronic papers gathered in a batch, they have undergone preliminary selection to select them according to their relevancy. In this stage also the partition of dissertation roughly drafted to cluster each topic in proper order. Stage one and two most of time was done concurrently.

2.2.3 Review of Literatures

The third stage is the review of literatures where valuable information being extracted and rewritten in own writing properly. The finding of more research articles will be continuously done in order to meet the target of more than 60 papers.

2.2.4 Information Synthesize and Interpretation

Some interpretation and summarization being added into review writing in chapter four and the remaining will be in sequenced chapter five. This is the fourth stage; it is highly related to previous stage of literature review. Most of important things that have been identified brought into conclusion of dissertation as the summary and points to emphasize the finding.

2.2.5 Report Writing and Submission

The final stage is writing stage of the dissertation component neatly with proper order and formation before wrapping it as a whole. Fig. 2.1 provides the flow chart of overall research activities. The dissertation is written in such way consisting of five main chapters as being stated in previous; they are:

- i. Chapter I: Introduction
- ii. Chapter II: Methodology
- iii. Chapter III: Fundamental of Study
- iv. Chapter IV: Review of the Literatures
- v. Chapter V: Conclusion

Fig. 2.1 Flow chart for all related works which involved.

2.3 GANTT CHART

This work starts at the middle of September 2014 after days from beginning of semester and to be completed after two semesters. In order to organize and track the progression of this research project, a simple Gantt chart was constructed as in Table 2.1. All explained steps in previous were tabulated chronologically to provide reader with clear path of this dissertation and also as a guide for the author in his work to deal with datelines. For the information, the numbers below the ‘year’ in the table representing the month; for example at the beginning, 9 stand for September 2014 and the exact case goes for the followings.

Table 2.1 Gantt chart for the whole activities.

Research Activity	2014				2015						
	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Collection of Literature	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Selection of Literature		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Chapter I, II and III			x	x	x	x	x				
Key Milestone 1					K1						
Review of Literature				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Summarization				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Writing & Submission			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Key Milestone 2											K2

There are two milestones put in the chart; they were denoted by bolded K1 and K2 at every end of semester. At the end of first semester (K1), manuscript for first and second chapter is submitted for fair evaluation; however previous three activities before this milestone not ended at this mark. Completely written dissertation after good agreement with supervisor is preceded to the submission for evaluation at K2 and concludes the overall works.

2.4 KNOWLEDGE MAP

Fig. 2.2 provides the point of contribution of this work in the body of knowledge.

Fig. 2.2 Point of contribution and discussion in the body of knowledge.

CHAPTER III

FUNDAMENTAL OF STUDY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Silicon is an organic material that has been use in making high efficiency solar cell and also electronics component. Silicon is an element having 4 valence electrons in which every of them tightly bounded by covalent bond among neighboring atom. Pure silicon is a poor electrical conductor; thus doping with 3 valence electrons element (such as boron) to create p-type semiconductor or with 5 valence electrons element (such as phosphorous) to create n-type semiconductor is necessary in order to enable required electrical conductivity. Fig. 2.1 shows how the substitution of doped atom into silicon takes place and respectively, the extra electron and also a hole which consequence of missing electron in each type will present.

Fig. 3.1 Two type of silicon after doped: (a) N-type silicon doped with phosphorus atom, and (b) p-type silicon doped with boron atom.

The photon with specific wavelength (λ) and energy carried equal to band gap value of silicon semiconductor will be absorbed by the atom and excite the electron in valence band into conductor band and leaving a hole. The mechanism is referred as the generation of exciton, takes place in active layer of material which is in between the n-type and p-type region as shown in Fig. 3.2. N-type region of silicon have extra valence electrons due to doping enable the movement of electron and this region is connected to the conductor (negative electrode) to collect and flow the electron into external circuit. In other hand, p-type will enable imaginary ‘hole movement’; connected to another conductor (positive electrode) and the electron and hole will be recombined just after entering the region.

Fig. 3.2 Schematic of working principle for a PV solar cell.

Crystalline silicon is inorganic material for solar cell. It might be monocrystalline silicon (c-Si) with very neat and consistent crystal alignment thus the raw price generally higher than multicrystalline (mc-Si) counterpart which still having crystal structure but inconsistent size and arrangement. Another type of solar cell is organic, thin film based deposition and photoelectrochemical solar cell with lower efficiency compared to crystalline silicon solar cell. Most common type of monocrystalline silicon that used as a starting material in is grown by mass scale Czochralski (CZ) process in diameter of 300 mm (standard), 200 mm and 150 mm by crystal pulling from the melt. The CZ process is acceptable for electronics manufacturing and solar cell because of small number of defect and higher production cost at lower cost compared with float zone (FZ) silicon. Despite of that, for the application that demand high purity of material, they opted FZ silicon; the reason why

CZ become more preferable also because of not much the condition where this high purity is favored. Meanwhile for the thin film silicon based solar cell, the type of silicon being used is either amorphous (a-Si) or microcrystalline ($\mu\text{c-Si}$). Silicon after ingot CZ or FZ ingot sawing in default is a poor light absorber especially at longer wavelength of visible light. The absorption coefficient of silicon at 300K as calculated and tabulated by Green & Keevers (1995) can be represent in Fig. 3.3. The reflectance as in Fig. 3.4 then can be determined based on refractive index.

Fig. 3.3 Absorption coefficient of flat c-Si wafer at 300K in λ range 250-1450nm.

Fig. 3.4 Reflectivity of flat c-Si wafer at 300K in visible range.

3.2 PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTIC OF SOLAR CELL

3.2.1 Current and Voltage

The performance of certain solar cell is determined by several characterizations or benchmarking techniques. Test of current-voltage (I-V) measurement is almost necessary in order to observe the output voltage and current, hence determined the output power and the fill factor of photoconversion. Alternatively, the measurement of current can take in density form; the current for every cell area (J). The test takes place in dark condition or under illumination of standard test condition (STC = 25 °C, 1000 W/m² irradiation and air mass 1.5G). The I-V or J-V characteristic of solar cell has a non-linear form, highly dependent on the amount of exposed radiation and temperature. Fig. 3.5 shows the output curvature of current and voltage for a working solar cell under standard test condition; the maximum power extraction from the cell corresponding to the radiation and temperature is located at ‘mpp’ subscript.

Fig. 3.5 Dark and illuminated J-V, P-V characteristic of solar cell.

Open circuit voltage is the maximum voltage at zero current (open circuit) denominated by V_{OC} and J_{SC} is representing the maximum current density output at zero voltage (short circuit). Since the power is obtained from multiplying the voltage

and the current, the maximum power output (P_{mpp}) of solar cell lies in region of optimum value for both current (I_{mpp}) and voltage (V_{mpp}) in which can be obtained from the I-V curve. The efficiency of the solar cell can be determined based on the fill factor and the power contained in incident light (P_i) which represented by simple formulation as follows:

$$FF = \frac{I_{mpp} V_{mpp}}{I_{sc} V_{oc}} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{J_{mpp} V_{mpp}}{J_{sc} V_{oc}} \quad (3.1)$$

The efficiency in term of fill factor can be related as below. Theoretical perfect value (100 %) fill factor is referred if interpolation of V_{oc} and I_{sc} has to been made. However, so far this is not the main concern as no cell yet could achieve 100 % fill factor due to parasitic loss that occur everywhere in the cell.

$$Eff = \frac{FF \cdot I_{sc} V_{oc}}{P_i} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{FF \cdot J_{sc} V_{oc}}{P_i} \quad (3.2)$$

3.2.2 Series and Shunt Resistance

A solar or PV cell can be modeled as one-diode equivalent circuit as in Fig. 3.6 in order to understand its electronic behavior with the presence of base electronic component in which their behavior is well known.

Fig. 3.6 One diode equivalent circuit model for PV devices.

Series resistance (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) being added into the circuit to represent non-ideal solar cell which comply with practice. The equilibrium of currents flowing in the circuit then can be written as:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(\exp \left(\frac{q(V + IR_s)}{mk_B T} \right) - 1 \right) - \frac{V + IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3.3)$$

In the formulation, I_{ph} is the photocurrent, I_0 is the equivalent diode inverse saturation current, q is the value charge of electron, m is diode ideality factor, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T is temperature of the cell. The value of R_s is contributed from ohmic resistive losses in various places in the cell in between contact of semiconductor and metal such as at emitter and base. In ideal device, the value of R_{sh} is infinity but finite in actual device. This value was determined by alternative current path short circuiting the diode. Increasing the R_s will decrease the J_{SC} and FF while in other hand, decreasing the R_{sh} will decrease the V_{OC} and FF. Both R_s and R_{sh} can be determined by slope of the graph of illuminated I-V curve as in Fig. 3.3 before. R_s take the slope at near V_{OC} point and R_{sh} take at near I_{SC} point with basic slop determination as follow:

$$R_s = \frac{\Delta V_{OC}}{\Delta I_{OC}} \quad \text{and} \quad R_{sh} = \frac{\Delta V_{SC}}{\Delta I_{SC}} \quad (3.4)$$

3.2.3 Quantum Efficiency

The quantum efficiency of solar cell is being calculated from the measured spectral response (SR). This SR prior can be explained as a ratio of output current generated from the device upon incident of incoming photons; the unit taken is current/power (A/W). The relationship between the SR and QE is:

$$SR = \frac{q\lambda}{hc} QE \quad (3.5)$$

The quantum efficiency indicating the electrons output by the cell in respect to the number of photons which incident into. The definition can be further separated into two; the internal quantum efficiency (IQE, or just QE) and external quantum efficiency (EQE) as below:

$$EQE(\lambda) = \frac{\text{Electrons collected as photocurrent, per second}}{\text{Photons incident, per second}} \quad (3.6)$$

$$QE(\lambda) = \frac{\text{Electrons collected as photocurrent, per second}}{\text{Photons absorbed, per second}} \quad (3.7)$$

Both of QE and EQE are the function of wavelength, λ . The perfect value of quantum efficiency is remain constant at 1.0 across the wavelength as long as below the wavelength of bandgap ($E_g = hc/\lambda$), for example silicon having E_g around 1.1 eV thus the maximum wavelength for photon absorption must not exceed 1100 nm or nearby value. Shorter wavelength of photon in range of 350 nm to 450 nm (blue color) or nearby however faces common problem of front surface recombination and 700 nm and above is due to rear surface recombination. The offset of curvature from perfect value is contributed by reflection and a low diffusion length.

3.3 EFFECT OF TEXTURIZATION: THEORETICAL

3.3.1 Effect of Optical Loss Reduction on Performance

According to Basore (1990), front surface texturization contributes to improvement in current generation by photovoltaic effect in the conventional silicon solar cell by three different phenomenon/mechanism; they are:

- i. Reduction of front surface reflection.
- ii. Absorption of photons closer to the collecting junction.
- iii. Trapping of weakly absorbed photons within the cell.

The simplest situation to explain the phenomenon would be using the model of single crystal-etched surface, as shown in Fig. 3.7. The (100) silicon after anisotropic etching leave the pyramids structure which exposed to (111) facets with angle of 54.7° . In term of thicknesses, in most cases the texture surface is deeper than the emitter diffusion layer but shallower compared with the base of remaining silicon (denoted as W in the figure).

Fig. 3.7 Optical model for extended IQE analysis.

Source: Basore 1993

Incoming photon (λ) considered coming in normal direction to the plane arrived at the inclined surface and get reflected at the external front surface for a small portion of them (R_{fe}). Later, the remaining photons were refracted upon entering the facet (T_1) with the angle which determined by the inclination of the facet and wavelength dependent index of refraction (θ_1). For chemically textured (100) silicon producing (111) pyramids, the angle will be 41.8° for wavelength around 900nm (Basore 1990; Basore 1993). Photons with energy near to silicon bandgap being allow be transmitting into the silicon and reflecting at the back surface of the cell (R_{b1}) according to the condition of the surface; if it is polished, photons will be reflected at the same incoming angle ($\theta_1=\theta_2$) but if it is textured, random angles will take place (Lambertian reflector). More on Lambertian light trapping limit calculated by Green (2002). Finally, photons arrived at the front textured surface again (T_2) and some of them will be escaped out (R_{esc}) but major of them being reflected back inside because of exceeding the critical angle for total internal reflection (slight inaccurately illustrated in Fig. 3.5 as θ_2 need to exceed critical angle, θ_c); these phenomena known

as light trapping and the process will continue as photons bounced back and forth as denoted by n^{th} of every angle, transmittance and reflectance.

Internal quantum efficiency (IQE) refers to the efficiency with which photons that are not reflected or transmitted out of the cell can generate collectable carriers while the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of a silicon solar cell includes the effect of optical losses such as transmission and reflection. The numerical modeling and analysis for IQE being employed in order to explain and represent the internal operation of the cell (Basore 1990; Basore 1993). The purpose of the modeling using quasi-one-dimensional (Q1D) model as elaborated in the articles enable the evaluation of recombination parameters at the base and also determines the internal optical reflectance at the front and the back surface. The spectral response being adjusted to take the consideration of optical reflectance and finally lead to internal quantum efficiency which as stated as below:

$$\text{IQE} = \text{SR} \cdot \frac{q}{q_0} (1 - R_f) \quad (3.8)$$

If the quantum efficiency of solar cell affected by the spectral response, the spectral response which near bandgap itself depends on those following recombination parameters and optical reflectance; they are diffusion length in the base, back surface recombination velocity, external front surface reflectance, back surface reflectance, and also the internal front surface reflectance. However, while the internal quantum efficiency shows much dependence on diffusion length in the base, back surface recombination velocity and back surface reflectance, it almost not affected by internal front surface reflectance as the spectral response do. This internal quantum efficiency analysis seems better interpreted with the graph inverse of it (IQE^{-1}) versus inverse of absorption coefficient (α^{-1}), but need to consider about ‘extended IQE analysis’ in which extrapolating the slope of near bandgap wavelength instead of only taking first linear regime which occur at near infrared wavelength. Increasing in diffusion length in the base improve the internal quantum efficiency also highlighted by Saha et al. (1992) throughout the whole spectrum. This situation happens when the minority carriers diffusion length is much larger than the thickness of the base due to the reduction of front surface reflection coefficient, not forgetting the increase in the

absorption coefficient. At the same time, open circuit voltage actually decrease a bit for large diffusion length but in overall, the efficiency still increase for every increase in textured surface.

Current density is obtained by allocating the amount of generated current for every piece of solar cell area. The output of current density by the solar cell (J) depends on several factors; they are collection efficiency of photogenerated current (η_c), photon flux density (F), total external reflectance of light leaving the active surface (R_{total}), absorption coefficient (α), and also the thickness of solar cell material (W) as described by Rand & Basore (1991). The relation all of them identified summarized into a formulation as provided below. Note that the calculated value is specific for every wavelength of photon.

$$J(\lambda) = \eta_c(\lambda) q F(\lambda) [1 - R_{total}(\lambda)] [e^{-\alpha(\lambda)W}] \quad (3.9)$$

IQE is depends on output current density and EQE can be related with IQE after taking factor of reflectivity into account. Based on previous formulation of current density, both IQE and EQE can be written in term of light reflectivity such as following equation:

$$IQE(\lambda) = \frac{J(\lambda)}{q F(\lambda) [1 - R_{total}(\lambda)]} = \eta_c(\lambda) [e^{-\alpha(\lambda)W}] \quad (3.10)$$

$$EQE(\lambda) = IQE(\lambda) [1 - R_{total}(\lambda)] \quad (3.11)$$

In actual cases, even though the surface of silicon solar cell for example not was being textured, there are still chances of light trapping phenomenon inside the material at rear surface which can be considered to improve the IQE. The value of IQE for trapped light can be determined by taking the value of front reflectance; this value could not directly measurable as front reflectance is not measurable in a light trapping solar cell as claimed by the author.

3.3.2 Light Based on Surface Grating Model

According to Llopis & Tobias (2005) and Sai et al. (2007), there are minimum sizes of textured pyramids on the silicon surface in order to effectively reduce the light reflectance. Both of them are using the one dimensional model of surface grating to represent the diffraction of light during the incident with the surface (2 dimensional model also presented by Sai et al. 2007). The reflectance of light to neighboring structure and transmittance into the material comply with explanation provided by previous articles as per discussed re-introduced as shown in Fig. 3.8.

Fig. 3.8 Ray trajectories in the geometrical optics description for the textured surface of silicon wafer.

Source: Llopis & Tobias 2005

Once the light travelled from the air into the silicon, they will be diffracted with specific angle and order. Relating the explanation presented by Llopis & Tobias (2005) with Sai et al. (2007), one dimensional surface grating with forward diffraction angle θ_m can be written as:

$$n_2 \sin \theta_m = n_1 \sin \theta_i + m \frac{\lambda}{D} \quad (3.12)$$

The refractive index of medium 1 and 2 in which light traveling from and into denoted by n_1 and n_2 respectively; θ_i is a incident angle of light while the θ_m is the diffraction angle of m^{th} order ($m=0, \pm 1, \dots$). The zero order ($m=0$) was indicating for refraction and reflection for a flat surface, without the influence of textured feature (or insignificant size of grating features). The period of grating is denoted by D and this

phenomenon is non-dependent on the depth of the grating (h) which all of them stated previously marked in the Fig. 3.9.

Fig. 3.9 One dimension surface grating illustrating the geometry of diffraction by a periodic structure with the propagation of different diffraction orders.

Source: Llopis & Tobias 2005

If the situation is being considered as 2 dimensional (no illustration provided), the diffraction angle for normal incident angle can be written as below. Note that θ_{mn} and ϕ_{mn} stand for diffraction polar angle and the azimuthal angle for diffraction order of (m,n) . The refractive index of silicon, n_{Si} taken as a 3.6 constant.

$$n_{Si} \sin \theta_{mn} \cos \phi_{mn} = m \frac{\lambda}{D_x} \quad (3.13)$$

$$n_{Si} \sin \theta_{mn} \sin \phi_{mn} = n \frac{\lambda}{D_y} \quad (3.14)$$

The limit of very large texture feature defined with ∞ ratio of D/λ while the limit for very small feature is $D/\lambda \rightarrow 0$. According to Llopis & Tobias (2005), the order except the zeroth order ($m=0$, flat surface condition) can only present if the size condition of D larger than $m\lambda_{\min}/n_1$. The texture found that not significantly modify the reflectivity and more likely similar to polished surface if the grating (pyramid size)

$D < 20$ nm; only sufficiently big structure for $D = 300$ to 400 nm (0.3 to $0.4\mu\text{m}$) result to closer to ray tracing calculation data, leaving the reflectivity curve for polished surface. Sai et al. (2007) more emphasize on the aspect ratio of the grating feature, depth over period (d/D). They found that surface reflection loss can be reduced by employing wider range of grating period from 0.1 to $1.0\mu\text{m}$ (instead of 0.3 to $0.4\mu\text{m}$ in previous) but need appropriate aspect ratio to feature height (example given $d/D = 4.0$). The texture size smaller than $0.2\mu\text{m}$ need to have higher aspect ratio to help lower reflection losses and big texture (larger than $0.5\mu\text{m}$) lead to better light trapping for photon with wavelength of 900 to 1100 nm.

3.3.3 Surface and Base-dopand Concentration

Considering the increment in surface area in the silicon after texturization, adjustment is necessary in calculation for determination of base-dopand concentration. The relationship between capacitance and voltage with the base-dopand concentration can be express as:

$$N_A = -\frac{2}{A_{ju}^2 q \epsilon_0 (\epsilon_r C_{cell}^{-2} / V_{cell})} \quad (3.15)$$

The q , ϵ_0 and ϵ_r represent constant values of elementary charge, vacuum permittivity and dielectric constant of silicon respectively. Capacitance-voltage (CV) measurement can be used to determine the dopand concentration, N_A but need to consider the area enhancement factor of textured silicon surface. Hinken et al. (2010) use the ratio of emitter thickness, t and pyramid base length, l in order to calculate the reduced emitter thickness, $t_r = t/l$. This kind of analytical determination is quite valid only for prescribed textured surface by alkaline wet etching which producing the pyramid point angle $2\alpha = 70.53^\circ$ with rounded-shape of its bottom. For the textured c-Si which comes from different suppliers, the area enhancement factor, f (the ratio of active area of junction, A_{ju} relative to the macroscopic area, A_{macro}) is 1.48, 1.4 and 1.1; they found that this can be obtained from the ratio of the pyramid base length and the emitter thickness.

However, Wang et al. (2011) remarks that erroneous of geometrical correlation method from Hinken et al. (2010) still occur if only simple matter such as scale of junction area taken into consideration. While it is valid determination for sample pyramids with size of $4\mu\text{m}$, it is not as exact case of $1\mu\text{m}$ sized pyramids when its depletion region was significantly distorted by the geometry. The simulation of the 2D junction electrostatics invalidates the correction method as the edge of the depletion region does not really follow the junction in $1\mu\text{m}$ sized pyramids texture (Fig. 3.10).

Fig. 3.10 Simulation of 2D junction electrostatics to investigate the correction method: (a) $4\mu\text{m}$, and (b) $1\mu\text{m}$ sized pyramids texture.

Source: Wang et al. 2011

3.4 AR COATING AND ENCAPSULATION

The deposition of anti reflection (AR) coating on the top of emitter proven enhance the reduction of optical losses, stack very well with effect of texturization. Improvement in current generation as discussed previously ultimately leads to better fill factor with deposition of AR coating, as simple demonstrated by Salwa et al. (2009) in which using SiN_x layer by PECVD. Such layer acts as passivation for the surface, reducing the carrier recombination which almost desired for solar cell application. Otherwise, with lower energy of deposition, one can opted for passivation by intrinsic or doped hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) but with certain limitation in which they cannot withstand significantly higher temperature from their deposition temperature without degradation. Not limited to that, double passivation layer also could be employed, for example as demonstrated by Li et al. (2011) which depositing a-Si:H layer on the silicon substrate and followed by SiN_x :H both by PECVD. Right annealing of the stacked layer could further increase the effectiveness of the passivation which they offer.

For the complete assembled solar cell in the module, the light that particular multi-layer structure is determined by complex refractive index ($n_c = n - ik$) medium of encapsulation and the silicon cell. The simplest relationship is denoted by a formulation as below:

$$R = \frac{(n_{c0} - n_{c1})^2}{(n_{c0} + n_{c1})^2} \quad (3.16)$$

The integer of 0 is representing the medium of incoming light while 1 stand for the silicon, n is real refractive index, and k is the extinction coefficient in which both value of n and also need to know that k is a function of λ which can be obtained variously according to tabulated data by Green & Keevers (1995) and further completed by Green (2008). Float glass with low iron content is very common for this purpose; protecting the cell from harsh weather, provide UV resistance and also at the same time allow high transmission of photons for photovoltaic process (Deubener et al. 2009). The effect of optical confinement by using encapsulation is very crucial even noticeable for non-textured nominal planar samples. Gee et al. (1994) after producing the textured surface by mechanical and chemical method, measure the reflectance of complete fabricated cell in the glass encapsulation. They found that 50% of rays which reflected from the silicon surface experienced total internal reflection at interface between glasses (encapsulate material) and air, also 50% reduction in reflectance obtained for encapsulated textured silicon compared with the flat one.

Total internal reflection occurs at inner side of device if reflected photon which remaining from the cell exceed the critical angle, resulting toward much lower optical losses. All factors contribute dependently with each other; refractive index provided by the glass encapsulation, textured microstructure to further scatter inside and bounces the light to neighboring structure, and also back reflector to reflect back the unabsorbed light to the front surface. The schematic of traveling light path in the device is shown in Fig. 3.11.

Fig. 3.11 Schematic of incident light optical path in textured silicon surface.

Source: Santbergen & van Zolingen 2007

EVA stand for ethyl vinyl acetate and the optical properties is safe to be assumed similar to the glass on top of it, hence no significant in light diffraction expected. However while it is true that incorporating the encapsulation with the cell lead to better light confinement, small portion of light absorbed to the layer itself due to not perfect transmission material. For comparison, around 70% of incoming light absorbed by cell (silicon band-to-band absorption) and around 3% absorbed by glass (Santbergen & van Zolingen 2007); however in real situation it is actually depends on many other factors that should really be taken into consideration.

CHAPTER IV

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURES

4.1 PHYSICAL AND DRY METHOD

4.1.1 Mechanical Grooving

4.1.1.a Blades for Grooving

Gee et al. (1994) in their research articles presented the use of mechanical dicing saw and chemical etching to produce texture on multicrystalline silicon wafer. According to them, for mechanical dicing saw which producing the 45° groove (V-groove), minimum 30° pyramid angle is needed in order to successfully enable the double bounce reflectance. By using $90\mu\text{m}$ multi blades, the groove spacing also leaved with exact spacing of $90\mu\text{m}$. Etching the mechanically textured groove later reduce the pyramid's angle from 45° to 32° (Fig. 4.1); etching being done in $\text{HNO}_3\text{-HF}$ solution to remove residual damage from the mechanical texturing.

Fig. 4.1 Mechanical textured: (a) Before, and (b) after chemical etching.

Source: Gee et al. 1999

Unfortunately due to the significant reduction in pyramid angles, the textured wafer cannot proceed to solar cell fabrication due to large surface features which not suit with the photolithography process. Two groups from University of Konstanz, Germany; Fath et al. (1997) and Gerhards et al. (1997) employ the tool which consists of metal body with V-grooved surface coated with abrasive layer of diamond as shown in Fig. 4.2(a). The particle of diamonds sized in between 5 to 10 μm presence on the outer surface of 25mm length of tubular tool, rotated at 18,000 rpm with lateral cutting speed of 3 cm/s.

Fig. 4.2 Schematic of: (a) Wheel build of a metal coated with a diamond abrasive layer, and (b) principle of the roller printing technique.

Source: Fath et al. 1997; Gerhards et al. 1997

Mechanical texturization is be done by printing the structuring wheel which equipped with abrasive in order to achieve V-grooved surface on the silicon. In case of Fath et al. (1997), reasoning to the actual experiment and extrapolation, 1 million wafers could possibly textured by the designed cutting tool as described before recoated is needed with diamond abrasive particle, equivalent with 10% of its wear level. Or in unit of cost, it is around 0.025USD for every 10x10 cm² wafer, provided its details in Table 4.1 (texturization cost might only valid for that date comparison). As high as 35 mA/cm² short circuit current density reported with right curvature radii at the V-groove bottom. Additionally, in article of Gerhards et al. (2007), a new concept of mask free and self aligned metallization concept was disclosed which using roller printer as in Fig. 4.2(b); thick film paste deposited on protruding regions of the V-grooved silicon using a roller tool aiming for more simplification in production.

Table 4.1 Cost analysis for introduced mechanical texturization technology.

	Costs per unit (USD)	Costs per wafer (cents)
Investment costs	100,000–200,000	0.28–0.57
Fully automated structuring units: 2		
Depreciation time: 7 years		
Operational costs	2,000–3,000	0.04–0.06
Structuring wheel (100 mm long) uncoated metal body (5 times re-coatable)		
Coating with abrasive layer (nickel/diamond) 40 µm thick, tool wear after 1 million wafers	600–800	0.06–0.08
Cooling and rinsing water per unit: (8 l/min)	10 USD/m ³	0.6
Electrical energy (2 x 8 kW)	0.1 USD/kWh	0.1
Labor costs		
1 Operator (quality control/maintenance)	35,000	0.35
0.5 Technician (maintenance/repair)	55,000	0.55
Service / Repair	10,000	0.1
Total structuring costs per wafer		2.1–1.4

Source: Fath et al. 1997

4.1.1.b Double Surface Grooving

Terhaiden & Fath (2003) develop the double sided mechanically V-grooved in MECOR (MEchanically CORrugated) and BOSS (Both Sides perpendicularly Structured) texture configuration on FZ silicon sample as shown in Fig 4.3. In MECOR concept, front and rear side of silicon being grooved in parallel direction while in BOSS, they are perpendicular each other. For both concepts, metallization by using SAFE employed with defining contact area on flank area of a V-groove using shallow angle photolithography, SAP. For the textured rear surface of crystalline silicon wafer, recombination tends to occur more compared with polished surface.

Drop in cell efficiency observed by in their mechanically grooved silicon wafer, both in relative parallel and perpendicular direction between front and rear surface.

Fig. 4.3 Schematic of: (a) MECOR, and (b) BOSS concept.

Source: Terhaiden & Fath 2003

In the experiment, double sided textured silicon solar cell achieve notably high efficiency even by mechanically surface modification, 18.5% and 19.3% for optimized MECOR and BOSS cell respectively (Table 4.2). Front texture with polished flat rear surface in which reducing the effect of recombination slightly score a little bit higher than that figure though.

Table 4.2 Best cell parameter achieved from MECOR and BOSS concepts.

	Texture FS/RS (°) Contacting FS/RS	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	η (%)
MECOR	35/90 SAP&SAFE/ 2% mask	652	36.5	77.8	18.5
BOSS	35/90 SAP&SAFE, P2	650	38.0	78.1	19.3

Source: Terhaiden & Fath 2003

4.1.2 Reactive Ion Etching

4.1.2.a Metal Catalyst in RIE

Reactive ion etching (RIE) is another kind of dry etching which applying both physical and chemical mechanism to achieve fine resolution of etch and noticeably less time consumed for the process. The gases that being uses is similar to chemical dry etch process for example CH_4 , SF_6 , boron trichloride (BCl_3), and also others which is appropriate. The better textured surface possibly being achieved but the lower cost material of mc-Si wafer being adjusted with more sophisticated and costly process which involved. Zaidi et al. (2002) introduce the use of metal, Al and Cr as a catalyst in RIE. By using Cr catalyst, the structure sized in range 50 to 300nm diameter with separation in range 100 to 500nm depth obtained while by introducing Al catalyst, columnar profile sized around $1\mu\text{m}$ manage to be produced. Cr assisted RIE result to lowest hemispherical reflectance compared with Al assisted, both significantly shows reduction in optical losses from non-textured silicon sample.

4.1.2.b Etching Based on Electrodes

In the RIE vacuum chamber, there are 2 electrodes; one is RF powered while another one is connected to the ground. According to Prasad et al. (2010), wafer during the process if being placed at RF powered electrode will enable sputtering-dominated reactive ion etching or RIE mode. In other situation, if wafer being placed at ground electrode, it will enable mode of reactive species-dominated plasma etching. In term of light reflectivity of textured sample, they found that uniformly textured surface obtained with second setup which is on the ground electrode. Non-uniformity in textured microstructure resulted with on the powered electrode setup especially at the center of wafer, indicated by non-uniform darkening. This is because the combination of physical sputtering and chemical etching affecting the silicon sample, while it is not in case of wafer placed on the ground electrode in which the texturization was dominated by chemical etching. Lowering the RF power lead to more dependency on the chemical etching and more controllable process. The textured silicon yields the light reflectivity as low as 5% at 600nm. Treating the textured silicon with acidic

solution of HF-HNO₃ remove the damage afterward and rounding-off the sharp peaks; significantly increase the reflectivity resulted but further reduction to 2% obtained after deposition of SiN_x as AR coating layer as indicated in the Fig. 4.4.

Fig. 4.4 Diffused reflectance of mc-Si sample at different stages of cell fabrication.

Source: Prasad et al. 2010

4.1.2.c Masking and Unmasked REI

The REI etching for mc-Si texturization could either with the presence of mask or maskless; masking require additional step which is photolithography to define holes to be etched. According to Macdonald et al. (2004), although the masked REI gives the better microstructure and lowest light reflectivity of textured wafer, the relative difference between masked, unmasked REI and acidic wet etching reduced substantially after anti reflection coating deposition and encapsulation. Masked REI however still show better improvement in lower wavelength range from 300 to 450nm indicating its competency among others. Furthermore, it make possible to obtain neatly patterned structure as shown in Fig. 4.5 for comparison.

Fig. 4.5 SEM images of mc-Si after (a) maskless RIE textured with 5000x magnification, and (b) masked RIE pyramids with 2000x magnification.

Source: Macdonald et al. 2004

4.1.3 Gas Dry etching

The chemical dry etching is a dry etching which being carried using gas to attack the silicon surface, differently from REI. This process normally etch with isotropic behavior (etch rate similar regardless of crystal orientation) and exhibit high selectivity, however anisotropic dry etching in other hand offer the ability to etch with finer resolution and higher aspect ratio compared to the isotropic dry etching. Saito & Kosuge (2007) reported on producing the honeycomb-textured structure on both c-Si and mc-Si wafer using Ar gas and chlorine trifluoride (ClF_3) at room temperature; more environmental friendly gas which can easily trapped and decomposed in a scrubber or by soda lime. By this method, quite similar shape and dimension of honeycomb structure could be observed indicating that its compatibility with both type of wafer (Fig. 4.6). Both of them result to around 20% light reflectivity in wavelength range of 500 to 900nm. Table 4.3 provides the resulted fabricated cell performance parameter of 17 and 20 min textured sample in the experiment compared with planar un-textured sample. Fill factor as high as 77.8% and more than 12% efficiency recorded.

Fig. 4.6 SEM images of the textured surfaces using 20 minutes ClF_3 dry etching on:
(a) Monocrystalline, and (b) multicrystalline silicon wafer.

Source: Saito & Kosuge 2007

Table 4.3 Fabricated c-Si cell performance characteristic under AM1.5G.

Etching time	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA/cm^2)	FF (%)	η (%)
Un-textured	0.54	22.9	73.9	9.2
17 min	0.55	29.6	77.8	12.7
20 min	0.55	30.3	74.1	12.4

Source: Saito & Kosuge 2007

Those honeycomb structure resulted with prior masking of thermally grown oxidation prior to etching, patterning pinholes with a diameter of 0.01mm with a distance of 0.03mm. Kohata & Yaito (2010) texture monocrystalline silicon by using similar type of etching gas but without the masking layer. In the experiment, very small submicron random textured surface obtained as the result of isotropic etching behavior of the process and shows the improvement in light reduction in short wavelength, 17.8% at 600nm. This might due to the textured structure size is smaller than the wavelength; multi reflection is more likely prevented at wavelengths larger than size of the textured structures. Complete fabricated cell using textured silicon

surface result to around 37 mA/cm² in short circuit current density, improvement about 32% compared with planar cell.

4.1.4 Direct Laser Ablation

4.1.4.a Heat Damaged Surface

The last method of dry process that pin out our interest is laser texturization which is based on laser ablation. Instead of chemical dry etching to remove the silicon surface area, this method employ subsequent melting and evaporation under radiation absorbed by the material and generated by a pulsed laser. Dobrzanski & Drygala (2008) in their experimental work produce the simple textured structure on mc-Si wafer surface which is parallel grooves, similar concept with V-grooves by mechanical texturization. Such limitation that exists in this process is the melting of silicon that can be found at bottom and sidewalls of the groove (heat affected zone), caused by heat from laser itself and also enabling the deposition of foreign materials during the texturization. Thus, some thickness of grooved wafer needs to undergo material removal by etching to removal the damaged layer and fix the yielded cell efficiency, as tabulated in Table 4.4 for comparison.

Table 4.4 Performance comparison laser textured wafers.

Texture Type	Thickness Removed (μm)	Effective Reflectance (%)	Efficiency (%)
Without texture	–	34.08	10.21
Laser texture	–	13.96	0.56
Laser texture after removal of laser induced damage layer	20 40 60 80	17.49 20.53 23.78 28.53	2.02 6.85 9.44 10.51

Source: Dobrzanski & Drygala 2008

As much as 80 μ m thick laser textured damaged layer after being etched off from the surface demonstrate the efficiency of 10.51% in the fabricated cell, not much performance leap from un-textured sample which is 10.21% efficiency.

4.1.4.b Amorphous Debris Residue

Zielke et al. (2012) demonstrate the use of direct laser texturing (DiLaT) on FZ c-Si and mc-Si wafer without masking. No additional step of applying and removing the dielectric layer of masking required but the pattern itself defined by the laser movement. The important point in this method is the control to obtain desired high depth-diameter ratio which can its ability in light trapping. In this direct laser texturization, depth of the structures possibly should be lower than the thickness of metallization layer in order to avoid additional resistance losses; this could be achieved by minimizing the tubs diameter. The positioning of the laser spot is made possible by enabling ‘on the fly’ mode and moving the silicon wafer on the X/Y-table (2 directional). Two steps of cleaning is employed which involves the use of high concentration NaOH etching for short duration of time to remove the amorphous debris and later followed by etching in HF-HNO₃ solution to remove heat-damaged silicon. Table 4.5 provides the performance comparison between proposed DiLaT texturing with planar and alkaline etched samples, both for FZ c-Si and mc-Si.

Table 4.5 Performance of planar, alkaline etch, and DiLaT texturing.

Substrate	J_{sc} (mA/cm²)	R_{wgh} (%)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)
FZ Si Planar	35.8	16.0	679	75.3	18.3
mc-Si Planar	35.5	15.3	626	75.3	16.7
FZ Si Etch	40.6	6.9	660	77.5	20.8
mc-Si Etch	37.6	11.1	649	74.8	18.3
FZ Si DiLaT	40.6	5.7	665	73.6	19.9
mc-Si DiLaT	39.3	7.3	618	73.6	17.9

Source: Zielke et al. 2012

Etching depth (laser damaged) of $3.2\mu\text{m}$ result to best cell performance, 39.3 mA/cm^2 short circuit current density obtained for mc-Si cell with remarkably high 17.9% efficiency, while slightly higher values achieved by the FZ c-Si sample.

4.2 CHEMICAL WET ETCHING

Texturization of silicon surface for solar cell application using chemical wet etching is actually a subset of a whole subject of silicon etching that already broadly established in electronic industry, most notably in microelectronic and mechanical system (MEMS). In normal circumstances, smooth silicon surface after a portion of silicon removal (micro-machining) is the target and commonly highlighted in the article. However in solar cell application, the completely reversed situation is desired as partially etched surface will leave rough and textured microstructure.

4.2.1 Effect of Silicon Crystalline Orientation

The silicon might come from single orientation wafer from CZ or FZ process, or multi crystalline orientation. As the name given, mc-Si has different crystal orientation in the wafer so that the result from chemical wet etching should not be the same as c-Si due to this fact. Fig. 4.7 shows the illustration on every basic and simple crystal planes of silicon to indicate their position and correlation between each other.

Fig. 4.7 Silicon crystallographic plane indicates the (100), (110) and (111).

The silicon dissolved upon immersion into certain chemical. In general, the etchant either an alkaline or acidic solution; the main contrast between these two kinds of etchant is their etching behavior. The alkaline solution tends to etch direction dependently in which high etching rate in (100) and (110) compared with (111). So that, it is referred as anisotropic etching behavior and we should acknowledge the fact that different type of alkaline solution has different level of anisotropic. Most common anisotropic etchant being used in experiment and real industrial application are ethylenediamine pyrocatechol (EDP), potassium hydroxide (KOH), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and some others. Both of EDP and KOH etching can be found in article by Seidel et al. (1990), indicating the lowest etching rate in (111) silicon direction as shown in Fig. 4.8 and thus leaving the sidewall of (111) left un-etched in (100) and (110) silicon wafer.

Fig. 4.8 Lateral underetch rates using 50 % KOH at 78 °C as a function of orientation.

(a) The (100), and (b) the (110) silicon wafer.

Source: Saidel et al. 1990

Conventional KOH without isopropyl alcohol (IPA) additive etch better in (110) compare with (100) direction (Zubel & Kramkowska 2002; Zubel & Kramkowska 2004). The alcohol additive with more than one hydroxyl group further reduce the etch rate of the plane with (110) type bond configuration. Adding IPA into

KOH solution however does not affect the etching rate of (111) and (100) except lowering all the (hkl) silicon etch rate, shown in Fig. 4.9.

Fig. 4.9 Relative etches rates V_{hkl}/V_{100} in 10 M KOH and 5M KOH+IPA solutions.

Source: Zubel & Kramkowska 2004

In contrast of anisotropic etching, isotropic etching using acidic solution etches all direction with the same rate. Multi orientation silicon not effectively etched using alkaline solution because of its composed of various crystalline orientation while alkaline etch anisotropically with high etch rate in 110 and 100 direction as previous. So that, the texturization of multicrystalline silicon mostly using physical method or acidic solution. The common acid solutions are hydrofluoric acid (HF), nitric acid (HNO_3), acetic acid (CH_3COOH), or also mixture of HNO_3 - CH_3COOH -HF or HF- HNO_3 - H_2O which is common and suitable for texturing low cost industrial mc-Si cell (Gangopadhyay et al. 2007). However, it is not limited only to these three as alkaline solution also being used in several experiments. Vazsonyi et al. (2007) develops isotropic etching by adding NaOCl into NaOH solution. As the concentration of NaOCl which act as a strong oxidation agent increased, the etch rate of (111) also increased at the same time reducing the rate of (100). The tendency toward isotropic behavior is indicated by reduction of anisotropic (V_{100}/V_{111}) pure NaOH from 80-100 to only 4-4.5 at 50 % NaOCl concentration. More positive feedback on implementing this solution for industrial use of mc-Si texturing could be found in Basu et al. (2009)

and Basu et al. (2009) compared with acid in term of lower cost, better smoothness and more environmental friendly.

4.2.2 Effect of Conventional Etching on Pyramids Size

4.2.2.a KOH with IPA

In conventional KOH texturization, OH^- that supplied by KOH dissociation in water plays important role to react with silicon surface. According to Saidel et al. (1990), the etch rate, R determined by the available OH^- and free water particle as:

$$R = k_o [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^4 [\text{KOH}]^{1/4} e^{-E_a/kT} \quad (4.1)$$

However since the exact value of each coefficient not really our interest as the empirical formulation is depends on its experiment parameters (temperature and concentration) and its commonly being referred with more simpler manner which is $R \approx [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^a \times [\text{OH}^-]^b$ as used in several articles to highlight the importance of free water particles. Zubel & Kramkowska (2001) demonstrate the effect of IPA on etching rate using KOH. The etching rate simply increased at higher temperature of process, but not linear with increase in KOH concentration. This is because, initially increase in etchant concentration result to higher etch rate but after certain point where the concentration of KOH too high, the amount of free water in the mixture will drop due to excessive dissociation of KOH and consequently reduce the etching rate. However, IPA addition manages to increase the etching rate for high concentration of KOH; suggesting IPA plays roles in hindering hydration of K^+ and OH^- and enables more water particle to take part in the etching process by liberating the water particles in the close vicinity of silicon surface; improves the wettability by lowering surface tension (Zubel et al. 2011). High etching rate does not indicate the best surface texture for wafer to be use in solar cell application; in this case only with the use of 3 M of KOH result to desired rough textured surface and also not with IPA additive at saturation level. The solution of 3M KOH need 12% IPA to achieve saturation level, however

the near desired rough surface only be achieved with 5% IPA and pyramidal structure start to vanish with higher IPA concentration.

There were 6 stages in pyramids formation in KOH with additive texturization, shown in Fig. 4.10 (Nakamura et al. 2013). The additive which mixed into KOH play important role as the micro-mask; this kind of mask in other situation might build from hydrogen bubbles, native oxides, organic contaminations, or also trace metal elements.

Fig. 4.10 Mechanism of texture formation as suggested which consist of six stages: (a) Start (b) early stage (c) formation (d) deformation (e) reformation (f) small texture.

Source: Nakamura et al. 2013

Some of the additive particles adhered to the surface of wafer and at the top of micro pyramids. After a while, additive was removed on the top of pyramids and at this point, quite a deformation at the top can be observed. Additive later stick to the surface and lead to the formation of new pyramids. In case of slower etch rate, more new additive particle tend to stick at the new surface and it will result to increase in pyramids number with smaller size. Based on this, they suggest that the texturization actually dominated by the correlation among etching rate, adhesion rate and desorption rate of additives. Low concentration etching with KOH mixture generally

leaves the wafer surface uniformly populated by small upward pyramids in size of around $1\mu\text{m}$. Medium concentration etching result to bigger pyramids (around $2\mu\text{m}$) and the exact case in high concentration where large texture in size ranging from 3 to $5\mu\text{m}$ observed indicating the size of structure directly proportional with etchant concentration (Nakamura et al. 2013).

Park et al. (2009) replace the IPA with TBA (tertiary-butyl alcohol) as additive in KOH texturization of c-Si wafer. TBA has an extra CH_3 group, hence lower dielectric constant compared with IPA and enable etching which produce smaller pyramids texture (2 to $4\mu\text{m}$) and smoother compared with KOH-IPA (8 to $10\mu\text{m}$). Smoother surface however result to slightly higher light reflectance, 1.24% more in KOH-TBA compare with KOH-IPA counterpart. Due to the low boiling temperature of IPA which is around 82°C , the texturization process which holds on elevated temperature need to constantly added IPA. Therefore, this situation leads to difficulty in controlling the process and also higher consumption of IPA. Zobel et al. (2012) replace the use of common alcohol additive (IPA and TBA) in KOH with the alcohols with multiple hydroxyl groups: 1,2-pentanediol ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$). Commercial KOH-IPA however seems having slight advantages with 2% lower measured light reflection after the texturization, as shown in Fig. 4.11. At least, still the coefficient of light reflection close to 10% is attainable by using this proposed etchant mixture. High boiling point of 1,2-pentanediol which approximately 206°C is the main concern; it enable texturization bath at higher temperature than allowed IPA mixture indicating the competitiveness in lower health hazard (no alcohol evaporation), reduced process duration, and also cost saving in term of chemical loss.

Fig. 4.11 Reflectance etched c-Si in optimum KOH+1,2-pentanediol compared with KOH+IPA: (a) Before, and (b) after AR coating.

Source: Zobel et al. 2012

4.2.2.b NaOH with IPA

Vazsonyi et al. (1999) present the report regarding the texturization of c-Si using another alkaline solution with similar etching behavior, sodium hydroxide (NaOH). Low concentration NaOH with alcoholic additive with variation in texturization conditions was investigated upon (100) c-Si wafer. The etching rate with low concentration of NaOH in between 1.5 and 4.0 wt.% with low IPA concentration at 3 vol.% resulted to optimum texturization on the wafer. Any value of NaOH concentration outside that recommended range concluded to destroy the geometry of the pyramids. While the optimum concentration of NaOH is being used, the density of random upward pyramids is not sufficiently high; caused by high interfacial energy between the silicon surface and electrolyte, discourages the pyramid nucleation. The addition of IPA or neutral tenzid into NaOH improve the wettability and at the same time etch in (111) direction at recommended rate of 0.04 to 0.06 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$ result to more effective texturing with more pyramids coverage (Fig. 4.12). Lowest reflectance obtained after 55 minutes of process which is around 12.5%. Singh et al. (2001) use 2 wt.% NaOH with 20% IPA to explain about effect of texturing duration. During the early stage of texturization, small pyramids grown in sparse distribution and become larger with uniform coverage in optimum etching time in range of 25 to 35 minutes. At longer etch duration, some pyramids grow at the expense of others and lead to non-uniformity. In range 11 to 14% reflectance manage being obtained after 25 to 45 minutes of texturization in wavelength range of 400 to 1000nm.

Fig. 4.12 Pyramid formation mechanism without (left) and with (right) additive.

Source: Vazsonyi et al. 1999

4.2.3 Conventional Etching without Alcohol

4.2.3.a Using hydrazine hydrate

According to Gangopadhyay et al. (2006), the use of IPA as additive can be reduced and replaced by adding hydrazine hydrate (N_2H_4 , H_2O) into that particular alkaline solution. N_2H_4 , H_2O break into ionized state and supply necessary OH^- for texturization at high temperature more than 90°C . The experiment conducted with a batch of 25 wafers was textured for 30 minutes with initial IPA of 5% and being reduced in concentration in each following batch to 3.9, 2.85, 2.28% (total four batches). All four batches achieved good surface finish even with addition of lower concentration of IPA at every sequenced batch; at earlier batch hydrazine monohydrate might not dissociate at temperature of 82°C and gradually do so as time flows. Although uniform pyramidal texture on both wafers were observed, but in term of total reflectance over a broad wavelength range after AR coating deposition, conventional NaOH still slightly better than NaOH- N_2H_4 , H_2O (Fig 4.13a). The range of efficiency based on numbers of cell provided in Fig. 4.13(b). Larger pyramids size averagely around $10\mu\text{m}$ obtained by proposed etchant solution compared with conventional NaOH (2 to $3\mu\text{m}$).

Fig. 4.13 (a) Comparison of reflectance textured wafer using NaOH–N₂H₄, H₂O and conventional NaOH, and (b) yield percentage of batch process silicon solar cell.

Source: Gangopadhyay et al. 2006

4.2.3.b Metal Grid Technique

The strategy employed by Chu et al. (2009) to eliminate the use of IPA in KOH solution for c-Si texturization is by placing metal grid with sufficient clearance from the wafer surface. Bubbles can be confined by the opening of metal grid because of surface tension of those hydrogen bubbles. The presence of bubbles acts as ‘pseudo-mask’, promoting formation of large pyramids as long as the being constantly trapped on the silicon surface during the texturization process. In the experiment, the texturization bath that was used is 1 wt.% KOH solution with variation of etching duration and temperature. For the parameters of metal grid, square size opening varied by 1, 1.5, 2, and 3mm while the wafer-grid separation varied by 1 and 2mm. No agitation provided during the process. Referring to Table 4.6, the lowest weighted reflectance obtained at 15.1% with optimized parameters of 20 minutes process at 90 °C, grid with 2mm² opening and 1mm separation between wafer surface and grid.

Table 4.6 Combinations of etching temperature and time with grid opening.

Temp (°C)	Etch Time (min)	Grid Opening (mm ²)	Coverage (%)	Pyramid Size (µm)	Reflectance (%)
70	10	2 x 2	70	1–3	29.4

70	15	2 x 2	90	3–6	22.7
70	20	2 x 2	91	2–6	21.7
80	20	2 x 2	90	5–8	21.5
90	20	2 x 2	95	6–9	15.1
90	20	–	86	1–4	21.9
90	20	1 x 1	92	2–5	20.9
90	20	1.5 x 1.5	95	2–8	18.9
90	20	3 x 3	77	1–5	25.7

Source: Chu et al. 2009

Typical diameter of hydrogen bubbles is around 2 to 3mm; because of this, they found that 2mm separation from grid to silicon surface was too large to enable close contact between bottoms of bubbles with silicon surface. Too large separation will not make the bubbles function well as the etch mask and the bubbles trapping capability also decreased. Similar case can be related with the dimension of grid opening; wider opening assumed to allow masking with larger bubbles, but also need to consider the optimum size as the bubbles observed managed to escape at the edge or the surface of grid. Regarding the effect of etchant parameters, higher temperature and longer texturization duration result to higher etching rate while the grid size opening and clearance is unique of this experiment where it is just right to confine hydrogen bubbles that being released from KOH-silicon reaction.

In the article, they provide cost comparison between the proposed techniques with conventional KOH-IPA (Fig. 4.14). The overall cost for texturization can be reduced by omitting the cost spends on IPA in conventional KOH-IPA (0.066 USD/wafer) compared with proposed approach (0.017 USD/wafer).

Proposed approach	Conventional approach
Pre-treatment: 3 min. negative oxide etch in 8% HF solution at room temperature Material cost: 0.033 USD/wafer	Pre-treatment: 3 min. negative oxide etch in 8% HF solution at room temperature Material cost: 0.033 USD/wafer
Texturing with metal grid: 20 min. etch in 1% KOH solution at 90°C Material cost: 0.017 USD/wafer	Texturing with IPA: 30 min. etch in 3% KOH solution with 5% IPA at 80°C Material cost: 0.066 USD/wafer
Post-treatment: 5 min. HCl cleaning at 60°C + 1 min. 8% HF dipping followed by DI water rinsing Material cost: 0.055 USD/wafer	Post-treatment: 5 min. HCl cleaning at 60°C + 1 min. 8% HF dipping followed by DI water rinsing Material cost: 0.055 USD/wafer
 Total cost: 0.154 USD/wafer	

Fig. 4.14 The cost comparison between the proposed approach and the conventional KOH-IPA texturization process.

Source: Chu et al. 2009

The technique of using metal grid also reported by Li et al. (2010) except in the experiment, the etchant is Na_2CO_3 . The Na_2CO_3 with varied concentration of 12 to 20 wt.% and constant temperature of 95 °C being used to etch the c-Si wafer for 25 minutes. Without the use of metal grid, the optimum reflectance obtained at 18 wt.% of Na_2CO_3 (14% weighted reflectance in wavelength range of 300 to 1100nm) because of increasing in etchant concentration lead to higher etch rate and better pyramidal texture, however exceeding optimum concentration results to over etch and undesired higher reflectance. Next, the metal grid with varied grid opening (0.5, 1 and 2mm) which made from stainless steel was placed at varied distance from wafer surface (0.5 to 2mm) during the texturization using 18 wt.% of Na_2CO_3 at 95 °C for 25 minutes. The lowest reflectance obtained is 10.70%.

The metal grid does not participate in reaction between etchant and silicon and as a catalyst, but helps capture and remove hydrogen bubbles which stuck on the

silicon surface. They found that the suitable grid opening is 1mm^2 and the separation is 1mm in order to efficiently put away the bubbles and nearly 30% increase in etching rate. The comparison was made with conventional NaOH-IPA texturization (2.5% NaOH, 6% IPA, 85 °C, and 25 minutes); this process result to 10.81% weighted reflectivity, slightly higher than proposed method and not to mention also extra cost need to spend on chemicals. The conventional texturization takes 0.064 USD/wafer while the proposed Na_2CO_3 with metal grid process takes only 0.025 USD/wafer, provided in Table 4.7. In previous, Chu et al. (2009) manage to obtain with only 0.017 USD/wafer using KOH and metal grid.

Table 4.7 The cost comparison between proposed technique and NaOH.

Metal grids-based texturization	Conventional NaOH texturing
Na_2CO_3 conc. = 18%	NaOH conc. = 2.5%, IPAconc. = 6%
Temperature = 95 °C	Temperature = 85 °C
Time = 25min	Time = 25min
Material cost: 0.025 USD/wafer	Material cost: 0.064 USD/wafer

Source: Li et al. 2010

4.2.4 Texturization Using Alternative Etchant

4.2.4.a TMAH Solution

Tetramethyl-ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) would be good alternative for conventional KOH and NaOH etching solution to avoid contamination of potassium or sodium ions contamination on the wafer if not treated carefully after the process. Iencinella et al. (2005) report their work on texturization of c-Si wafer in batches using TMAH solution. The experiment starts with a fresh solution of 5% TMAH at 70 °C for 20 minutes of time with mechanical agitation but unfortunately non-homogenous texture on the surface obtain with isolated regions left un-etched. They tried to solve this non-homogeneity texture problem by varying TMAH concentration from 4 to 7%, etching duration 20 to 40 minutes and temperature variation from 70 to 80 °C. Low concentration 5% TMAH without additive at 70 °C seems needing the

texturization duration of 40 minutes in order to complete the pyramidal formation as in first run of 20 minutes flat surface observed indicating lack of anisotropic etching. The same solution can be used to texture for 10 rounds (10 wafers) with hemispherical reflectance obtained within 15% as in Fig. 4.15 (with comparison), indicating it has high reproducibility and promising in term of chemical and cost saving process.

Fig. 4.15 Reflectance of textured c-Si using same TMAH for subsequent processes.

Source: Iencinella et al. 2005

Similar result but not included by them for total 10 samples etched one by one in the same TMAH solution; after this point, non-homogenous texture obtained. Worth to mention, they believe that dissolved silicon in TMAH solution during the texturization increase the effectiveness of the anisotropic etching, if feasible a few decigram of silicon should added into the fresh solution (first round). Pakhuruddin et al. (2011) manage to texture silicon surface without any IPA or other additive but only varying the TMAH concentration and etching duration. By direct comparison of surface morphology under different TMAH concentration, moderate value of 5 wt.% only result to high density of upward pyramids up to 95% coverage as shown by SEM images in Fig. 4.16.

Fig. 4.16 Images of textured silicon using 5 wt.% TMAH for 10 minutes at 90 °C:
 (a) Cross-sectioned 15k magnification, and (b) tilted 10k magnification.

Source: Pakhuruddin et al. 2011

The optimum duration concluded to be 10 minutes; after the etching duration of 30 minutes, the density of pyramids reduces significantly suggesting the consequence of over etching. No acceptably high texture coverage achieved with 3 and 8 wt.% TMAH regardless of etching duration. The base size and height of individual pyramid is around 0.5 to 0.6 μm , very small and also the color of wafer after optimum texturization appear dark in color indicating the effective light trapping. In wavelength range of 400 to 1000nm, average reflectance as low as 7% manage to be obtained. This is low enough even though no IPA added into TMAH to help the texturization/wettability. However, there was disagreement with data presented by You et al. (2001) where the same 5 wt.% TMAH without IPA at 90 °C need longer time for complete formation of pyramids texture (20 to 30 minutes).

Texturization of crystalline silicon using TMAH with IPA additive demonstrated by Papet et al. (2006), with three different initial condition of sample which is as-cut, damage etched, and polished. The presence of IPA play similar role in KOH or NaOH which is to improve wettability of between the etchant (TMAH) and silicon surface. In their experiment, large hydrogen bubbles (3mm) were observed at the silicon surface, effecting the etching and size of pyramid structure because of pseudo-mask phenomenon. The IPA additive diminishes the adherence of hydrogen

bubbles. In order to determine the best point for that, IPA concentration being varied and they found that 9% IPA is optimum concentration for 2% TMAH; too large and too small pyramids will lead to higher light reflectance compare with medium and uniform pyramid texture. The agitation somehow affecting the process such to provide better removal of adhered hydrogen bubbles, especially by using ultrasonic waves which the comparison shown in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8 Weighted reflectance of samples etched in agitation conditions.

Type of agitation	As-cut wafer	Etched wafer	Polished wafer
No agitation	13.8	29.0	36.9
	13.6	22.9	30.0
	14.0	29.0	36.8
Stirring bar	12.4	20.6	17.6
	12.5	17.3	12.4
	12.1	23.4	18.0
Ultrasonic waves	12.4	12.4	12.7
	12.3	12.5	12.6
	12.2	12.4	12.4

Source: Papet et al. 2006

In another case, Ou et al. (2011) report the lowest reflectance which they obtain by using 10 wt.% TMAH and 6 vol.% IPA. It was observed that without IPA additive, there are large amount of bubble spots and later result to poor surface coverage of pyramid texture with damaged layer on silicon surface. Bubble spots disappear with addition and increasing of IPA concentration in the mixture, however with higher concentration of IPA more than 6 vol.% the uniformity of the size of pyramid decreased. Prolong the etching time of TMAH-IPA until 25 to 35 minutes enable the complete disappearance of damaged layer, lead to uniform pyramid coverage and result to lower light reflectance. TMAH after dissociation in the water supply the OH^- and $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ ions (TMA^+). Assumption has been made in which TMA^+ , $\text{SiO}_2(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$, and IPA slow down the rate of oxidation by OH^- and water. It was suggested that the addition of IPA into mixture which to remove the hydrogen

bubbles should not too low and too much in order to put absorption of $\text{OH}^-/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ equilibrium with absorption of $\text{TMA}^+/\text{SiO}_2(\text{OH})_2^{2-}/\text{IPA}$, thus enable more uniform pyramidal formation.

4.2.4.b Sodium Carbonate

The uses of sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) made popular by Nishimoto & Namba (2000) in which they would like to prove their speculation in capability of Na_2CO_3 to etch crystalline Si wafer and producing desired texture. The reason behind that is in previous experiment by another group (not included here), potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3) able to perform well without additional of IPA. Furthermore, Na_2CO_3 more competitive in term of lower price and mostly used in glass industry as a raw material. In the experiment, Na_2CO_3 solution varied its concentration from 8 to 23 wt.% and its temperature from 80 to 100 °C in order to determine the optimum etching parameter. They found that the total reflectance of textured wafer becomes lower with increasing the Na_2CO_3 concentration and the etching process also become better at higher temperature. Average total reflectance in between 11 to 12 % achieved with high concentration (23 wt.%) for 10 minutes texturization before become worse after 30 minutes, at high temperature near 100 °C as long as it is safe. Adding NaOH worsen the reflectivity as in Fig. 4.17 and will be discussed more in later.

Fig. 4.17 Comparison reflectance of textured c-Si using Na_2CO_3 with/without NaOH.

Source: Nishimoto & Namba 2000

Another similar result also obtained by Vallejo et al. (2007) by using 25 wt.% of Na_2CO_3 . The etching behavior of medium and high concentration Na_2CO_3 (15 and 25 wt.%) is different from low concentration. Increase the etching time detrimentally affects the textured silicon surface. Using high concentration (25 wt.%) Na_2CO_3 , high density and uniform pyramids structure was obtained in first 10 minutes of texturization as in Fig. 4.18(a).

Fig. 4.18 SEM of textured sample in Na_2CO_3 for: (a) 10 min, and (b) 40 min.

Source: Vallejo et al. 2007

After 20 minutes, pyramids grow larger in size up to $6\mu\text{m}$ and later after 30 minutes, the medium size pyramid developed at expenses of smaller one and result to non-uniformity in topography. If 40 minutes elapsed, small pyramids that located as filler between large pyramids disappear, leaving hole-like microstructure such as inverted pyramid (Fig. 4.18b). Due to this, increasing the texturing duration result to higher light reflectivity in textured wafer, but this only applied to medium to high concentration because low is otherwise. The Na_2CO_3 solution mixed with NaOH and sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3) in separate mixture to investigate the effect of adding each of them; NaOH to supply more OH^- ions while NaHCO_3 for CO_3^{2-} ions. The addition of OH^- found that detriment the texturization as increased in average reflectance observed but in other hand increasing in NaHCO_3 concentration in Na_2CO_3 result to decrease in reflectance. The equilibrium of mixture change with

addition of NaHCO_3 , not only supply more CO_3^{2-} ions but also might decrease OH^- concentration. So that, they suggest to etch the wafer using 20 wt.% Na_2CO_3 at 95 °C for 15 minutes, and also addition of 0.9 wt.% of NaHCO_3 in the composition reduce the time for only 7 minutes to achieve same average total reflectance (Fig. 4.19). The presence of NaHCO_3 also help in achieving texture with smaller size however they conclude that etching rate is actually remain at same as before. Carbonic ions and/or compounds in the mixture plays similar role as IPA to initiate pyramidal formation.

Fig. 4.19 Effect of etching time and average reflectance using Na_2CO_3 with NaHCO_3 .

Source: Nishimoto & Namba 2000

The result has a good agreement with quite similar experiment next done by Sparber et al. (2003) which propose recipe of 12 wt.% Na_2CO_3 and 1.5 wt.% NaHCO_3 , Marrero et al. (2007) with 12 wt.% Na_2CO_3 and 4 wt.% NaHCO_3 , and lastly Barrio et al. (2013) with 25 wt.% Na_2CO_3 and 4 wt.% NaHCO_3 . Except what being highlighted by Marrero et al. (2007), addition of NaHCO_3 into the solution found that lowered etching rate of silicon with increase of its concentration, in contrast with previous statement by Nishimoto & Namba (2000). The NaHCO_3 contribute to presence of more hydrogen bubbles during the texturization which act as barrier on the wafer surface, thus lowering the etch rate. Higher etching lead to formation of bigger pyramids; the consequence from this is it leave large surface area not being textured. Barrio et al. (2013) later added the explanation of HCO_3^- ions supplied by NaHCO_3 believed play an important role in moderating the etching reaction. Also, the ratio of $\text{NaHCO}_3/\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3$ which is 0.16 emphasized by the author; higher ratio than

recommended leave the excessive amount of HCO_3H^- ions and reduction of OH^- ions; if this occurred, etching could not be optimized.

4.2.4.c Tribasic Sodium Phosphate

Xi et al. (2003) carried out the texturization of c-Si using tribasic sodium phosphate ($\text{Na}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$). This kind of solution able to hydrolyze in water to supply OH^- ions to attack the silicon surface, in fact the concentration of hydroxyl ion is higher than in Na_2CO_3 . The effect of concentration, temperature and etching time using the solution investigated. The $\text{Na}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration varied from 5 to 12.5 wt.%, the temperature varied from 75 to 90 °C, and the process duration varied from 15 to 30 minutes. The texturization more likely favor the lowest concentration (5 wt.%) and lowest temperature (75 °C) as the average reflectance obtained with it (9.37 %) for 25 minutes process. However, these three parameters actually influence each other and quite inconsistent result obtained with random experiment, therefore it is advised within the report to comprehensively consider the entire factor in order to obtain low reflectivity. $\text{Na}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ does not need another additive to improve the etching process. Additional of IPA (result in Fig. 4.20), Na_2HPO_4 , and NaOH into the solution effect the texturization in undesired way which results to greater weighted (average) reflectivity.

Fig. 4.20 Reflectance of textured wafer by using 10 wt.% Na_3PO_4 , with/without IPA.

Source: Xi et al. 2003

IPA reacts with Na_3PO_4 and makes the solution appear cloudy; Na_2HPO_4 does not help to improve the process as in case of NaHCO_3 additive in Na_2CO_3 texturization. When NaOH added into Na_2HPO_4 solution, the concentration of phosphatidate (PO_4^{3-}) increased and leaves the detrimental effect upon the texturization. If in other etchant mixture, IPA (in KOH , NaOH or TMAH) or CO_3^{2-} (in Na_2CO_3) play important role in promoting bigger pyramids formation as a surface active agent, they suggest PO_4^{3-} or its compound also not being different. Short process duration, low solution concentration and temperature plus no additive make this proposed solution competitive.

4.2.4.d Sodium Acetate

A year after that, another texturization of c-Si using alternative solution of sodium acetate (CH_3COONa) presented by Xi et al. (2004); a chemical that much cheaper than Na_2CO_3 and $\text{Na}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Just like KOH , NaOH or other alkaline, sodium acetate also hydrolyze in water to supply OH^- as described in a reaction below:

At first, each wafer is being etched by 2.5 wt.% NaOH and 10 wt.% CH_3COONa , both at 85 °C for 35 minutes respectively. In the wavelength range from 240 to 800nm, NaOH texturization results to slightly lower average reflectance (19.05%) compared with CH_3COONa (20.55%). The etchant further optimized by mixing NaOH and CH_3COONa together; the NaOH concentration held constant 2.5 wt.% while the CH_3COONa concentration varied by 5 to 10 wt.% and also with temperature variation of 75 to 90 °C. This strategy actually proved successful with significant reduce in average reflectance for only 12 to 13% in wavelength range from 400 to 800nm, shown in Fig. 4.21. This indicate that the texturization favor higher concentration of CH_3COONa in NaOH and high process temperature.

Fig. 4.21 Reflectance of textured wafer using 2.5 wt.% NaOH with 10 wt.% CH_3COONa . Different amounts of IPA also up for comparison.

Source: Xi et al. 2004

Hence, acetate (CH_3COO^-) plays a similar role as IPA where to help texturization by ensuring wettability and make the hydrogen bubbles generated during the process leave the silicon surface, based on observation of textured morphology and amount of light reflectance. However, IPA and CH_3COONa should not mixed together into NaOH because their role cannot be played simultaneously, in fact it leave great detrimental effect on texturization if do so. Increasing the concentration of IPA into NaOH- CH_3COONa will increase the light reflectivity of wafer after the process.

4.2.5 Forming the Inverted Pyramids Texture

4.2.5.a Thermally Grown Oxide

You et al. (2001) report the use of TMAH to produce desired rough inverted and upright pyramidal texture on the surface of c-Si wafer. TMAH concentration was varied by 5, 15 and 25 wt.% while the variation in temperature were 70, 80 and 90 °C. The inverted pyramid texture be achieved by photolithography of thermally oxidized SiO_2 before undergo etching. Due to selectivity etching behavior of TMAH toward silicon and oxidized silicon, silicon surface smoothly etched without pyramidal hillocks and result to uniform inverted pyramid as patterned (Fig. 4.22) regardless of

variation in etchant temperature and concentration. At low concentration of TMAH, undercut rate is highest (nearly 60 nm/min) and the rate keeps decreasing with increasing the etchant concentration. The (111)/(100) etch rate of TMAH in order to produce inverted pyramid also acceptably high; the value represent divided etch distance of the (111) plane with etch depth of (100) plane.

Fig. 4.22 Inverted pyramids and a detailed image after etched in 5 wt.% TMAH at 70 °C for 30 minutes; masked with 3μm width oxide.

Source: You et al. 2001

Without the SiO₂ masking, etching in TMAH result to formation of upward pyramids and the most desired uniform distribution with low light reflectance achieved with 5 wt.% TMAH at elevated temperature of 70 to 90 °C for duration of 20 to 30 minutes. The optimum etch rate which result to rough surface morphology can be found at several points by varying the time, etchant concentration and temperature, however no uniform random upward pyramids reported can be achieved with high concentration of TMAH (25 wt.%).

Fan et al. (2013) report their work on producing the inverted pyramid structure on c-Si wafer surface using wet etching of alkaline solution with patterned mask. TMAH and KOH variation in concentration from 5 to 25 wt.% being used to etch the surface that have been masked by thermally oxidized SiO₂ layer and photolithographed to determine their undercut rate and the ratio of (111)/(100) etch rate. In general, undercut rate of TMAH is noticeably higher than KOH for every same concentration and also the increase in etchant concentration result to lower

undercut rate. The high undercut rate also complies with the report by You et al. (2001); in this case pattern on silicon surface for TMAH should need wider oxide mask compared with KOH. For the etch rate of (100) plane, etching rate of KOH not mistakenly exceed the TMAH. Increasing in KOH and TMAH concentration result to slightly lower etch rate of (100) plane as hydration in solution occur so that the amount of available water particles that help the texturization process decreased. The etch rate ratio (111)/(100) was determined by dividing the etched depth of the (111) plane by (100) plane; the depth of etched (111) plane calculated through multiplying overhanging oxide depth with 54.74° , as illustrated in Fig. 4.23.

Fig. 4.23 Determining undercut rates with schematic of cross-section textured silicon.

Source: Fan et al. 2013

The (111)/(100) etch rate ratio of TMAH as obtained experimentally by them was 2-3 times greater than KOH and the ratio rate also favor the low temperature and high concentration of etchant. This indicate that TMAH has lower anisotropic factor compared with KOH, another point win by TMAH also its lower etch rate of SiO_2 although in lower quality of SiO_2 by PECVD compared with dry oxidation SiO_2 for KOH. Thus, very thin of SiO_2 masking only required and allow lowering its oxidation temperature and time. The comparison of 5 wt.% TMAH and 5 wt.% KOH in etching of $2.5\mu\text{m}$ oxide with masking has been made. Extremely smooth (111) sidewall with sharp vertex obtained with TMAH etching while etching by KOH result to inverted pyramid with horizontal etching stripe which parallel to $\langle 110 \rangle$ orientation on the $\langle 111 \rangle$ sidewall due to its lower (111)/(100) etch rate ratio. Numbers of insoluble floccules residue observed on the surface of inverted pyramid from KOH etching as shown in Fig. 4.24 which is not desirable because lead to contamination.

Fig. 4.24 SEM images after etching: (a) 25 wt% TMAH, and (b) 25 wt% KOH.

Source: Fan et al. 2013

The lowest light reflectivity obtained at 30 minutes etching in 5 wt.% TMAH and 70 °C process temperature with 2.5 μ m oxide mask which is around 8.4% at 990nm wavelength. KOH counterpart result to slightly higher which is 9.05% at 990nm with the same parameters. After prolong the process exceeding the optimum point of 30 minutes, inverted pyramids start to collapsed result from overetching.

4.2.5.b Porous PECVD Oxide

Small thickness of c-Si wafer removal upon texturization being highlighted by Kim et al. (2010) with the use of PECVD to deposit low quality porous SiO₂ layer on the wafer surface. This technique is more cost efficient than the process which require photolithography where both are targeting to achieve inverted pyramid structure instead of typical upward pyramid. The deposition of porous SiO₂ is possible by varied low temperature PECVD (250 and 150 °C) because to let the etching process happen at pinholes. The 25% commercial TMAH solution in water at 90 °C is used to etch the substrate surface because of TMAH has the excellent selectivity between silicon and silicon dioxide compared with KOH and NaOH. The lower temperature SiO₂ (150 °C) deposited by PECVD results to higher density of inverted pyramids, also at the same time with the consumption of silicon kept at minimal. In order to determine the depth of etched silicon, a partial of grown oxide at 250 °C PECVD removed before etched in TMAH for 2 minutes. With etch rate of 980 nm/min in TMAH, removal of 4.9 μ m depth was expected.

The effect of texturization duration was studied by varying the etching process time by 30 seconds to 30 minutes. Four stages of texture formation were identified and provided in Fig. 4.25; stage 1: Formation of inverted pyramids at first 30 seconds to 3 minutes, stage 2: Coalescence of inverted pyramids after 5 to 7 minutes from starting point, stage 3: Mask removal and extinction of inverted pyramids after 10 minutes elapsed, and lastly stage 4: Formation of upright pyramids after 30 minutes of texturization.

Fig. 4.25 Four stages of texturization or formation as proposed explanation:

(a) Stage 1, (b) stage 2, (c) stage 3, and (d) stage 4.

Source: Kim et al. 2010

Based on Fig. 4.26, in wavelength range from 400 to 1100nm, lowest hemispherical reflectance obtained at stage 4 (around 13%) and followed by stage 3 (around 14%), however stage 4 actually the situation where inverted pyramids and deposited oxides washed out; this mean small thickness surface removal no longer valid. Thus stage 3 is still promising and its stated in the article that further optimization of etch mask and etch solution should results to lower reflectance compare with random upward pyramids texture.

Fig. 4.26 Hemispherical reflectance of samples at every four stages.

Source: Kim et al. 2010

4.2.5.c Silicon Nitride Masking

A technique of depositing silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) masking layer on the c-Si wafer surface prior to alkaline etching presented by Huang et al. (2013). Wafer that has been cleaned by using acetone and IPA undergo 13.56 MHz, 3.7×10^{-3} Pa RF sputtering process to deposit the film of Si_3N_4 with difference thickness of 14, 40, 50, 73, 82, and 102nm by mean of ranging the deposition time from 10 to 22 minutes. The etching process using 1.43M KOH and 0.32M IPA at 80 °C being applied on each masked wafer for 15 minutes in order to form the upward pyramids structure. Without the masking layer, those etching parameters result to sparse distribution of pyramids (42.5% coverage) with average pyramids size of 2 μm . High surface coverage (94.7%) with desired lowest average reflectivity of 12.3% in wavelength range of 300 to 1100nm obtained with moderate thickness of Si_3N_4 (73nm) masking followed by stated KOH-IPA etching. The low reflectivity was achieved due to the textured surface filled with high density of small pyramids. Fig. 4.27 provides the schematics on understanding the texturization process done on each different thickness of masking which taken from their original article as a part of explaining the mechanism.

Fig. 4.27 Schematic of texturization on different thickness of Si₃N₄ layer.

Source: Huang et al. 2013

In early stage of etching, some Si₃N₄ layer removed and sparse distribution of inverted pyramids formed with exposure to (111) plane. The inverted pyramid act as initial point for etching to form upward pyramids; uniformity and higher quantity inverted pyramids in moderate masking layer result to high density small upward pyramids after certain duration of KOH-IPA etching. In general, this technique suggests that by varying the thickness of masking layer, one can actually control the upward pyramids size.

4.3 EFFECT OF SAW DAMAGE REMOVAL

4.3.1 Defect Point as an Initiator

Wafers sawed from the ingot are either skip or undergo saw damage etching (damage layer removal caused by sawing) in either alkaline or acidic solution prior to texturization process. The comparison between alkaline and acidic saw damage etching done by Park et al. (2009) to investigate their effect after KOH texturization. Acidic solution for this purpose is a mixture of HF, HNO₃ and CH₃COOH with composition ratio of 1:2:3 + fluoric surfactant, while the alkaline is KOH solution. All wafers prior to saw damage etching were cleaned appropriately. Saw damage etching

using high concentration of KOH leave the wafer surface with lower roughness due to isotropic etching against (100) direction at rate $2 \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. Square shape with average of $10 \mu\text{m}$ width and $5 \mu\text{m}$ height was obtained as shown in Fig. 4.28(a). In other hand, acidic saw damage etching results to crater-like shape (shown in Fig. 4.28b).

Fig. 4.28 SEM images of the silicon surface after saw damage etched in:

(a) KOH, and (b) HF-HNO₃-CH₃COOH for 60 seconds.

Source: Park et al. 2009

The mechanism of etching for KOH was described in earlier writing, except isotropic behavior exhibited due to near complete etching. In acidic reaction, the silicon firstly oxidized by HNO₃ and later the oxidized layer was removed by HF to form complex of H₂SiF₆. CH₃COOH in the mixture acts as buffering agent which prevents the decomposition of HNO₃ into NO³⁻ or NO²⁻. Fig. 4.29 shows the illustration how the initial surface condition prior to wet chemical texturization takes place effect the point of pyramids formation, both by alkaline and acidic pre-treatment. Indirectly, it also suggests that the pyramidal formation initiated at the defect point as concerned in several number of articles. Lowest average reflection on completed solar cell with SiN_x layer as an ARC obtained with this acidic saw damage etched sample in wavelength range of 300 to 1100nm which is 5.30%, at the meanwhile alkaline saw damage etching sample is 6.17%. The efficiency value 12.9% and 67.4% fill factor achieved. Slightly lower value but still comparable obtained using standard KOH saw damage etching with KOH-IPA texturization where the efficiency efficiency and fill factor is 11.7% and 67.8% respectively. This is related

with pyramids density after conventional texturization which enhancement in number of initiation point as stated above. Lowest average reflection on completed solar cell with SiN_x layer as an ARC obtained with this acidic saw damage etched sample in wavelength range of 300 to 1100nm which is 5.30%, at the meanwhile alkaline saw damage etching sample is 6.17%. The efficiency value 12.9% and 67.4% fill factor achieved. Slightly lower value but still comparable obtained using standard KOH saw damage etching with KOH-IPA texturization where the efficiency and fill factor is 11.7% and 67.8% respectively. This is related with pyramids density after conventional texturization which enhancement in number of initiation point as stated above.

Fig. 4.29 Schematic of KOH texturization for different initial surface condition of wafer and resulted topography.

Source: Park et al. 2009

4.3.2 NaOCl as Alternative Solution

Alternative solution as sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) demonstrated its capability as saw damage removal which is as proposed by Gangopadhyay et al. (2007). The c-Si wafer pre-treated with 12% NaOCl bath for 15 min at 80 °C and comparison being made with 8 wt.% NaOH at 75 °C for 2 minutes before conventional NaOH -IPA texturization. Hot NaOCl solution breaks to produce NaCl and nascent O which acts as oxidizing agent. The carbon or organic contamination that present on the silicon surface will be oxidized and removed later by immersion in HF followed by DI water rinsing. The textured wafer was completed as a working solar cell with presence of

SiN_x layer. The sample with NaOCl pre-treatment achieved the fill factor of 75% and 15% efficiency compared with sample without NaOCl pre-treatment which is 53% fill factor and 9.90% efficiency as in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9 Cell performance with/without NaOCl cleaning prior texturing.

Sample	V _{oc} (mV)	I _{sc} (A)	FF (%)	η (%)
Without NaOCl pretreatment	600	4.50	53	9.9
With NaOCl pretreatment	606	4.80	75	15.0

Source: Gangopadhyay et al. 2007

In similar, Basu et al. (2013) use the mixture of KOH-NaOCl for saw damage etching. As known, NaOCl is a strong oxidizing agent. NaOCl ionized in the water to supply hypochlorous ions (OCl⁻) and later breaks to release OH⁻ which necessary for silicon oxidation. Available sodium ions (Na⁺) from NaOCl and hydroxyl ions (OH⁻) from reaction of hypochlorous ions with water later combined to produce NaOH. This newly composed NaOH acts as etchant and continues to etch the silicon surface. The reaction also grows a thin layer of silicon dioxide which later acts as mask to reduce the etching rate and result to nucleation of smaller pyramids. Cells fabricated using saw damage etching prior to texturization with presence of SiN_x as an ARC result to lower reflectance which is 1.9% in wavelength range from 300 to 1000nm, while another sample which is NaOCl only is 2.1%. Despite of that, NaOCl saw damage etch followed by KOH-IPA texturization manage to obtain better fill factor, 79.1 and efficiency, 18.1 % compared with KOH-NaOCl damage etch which is 77.3 and 17.6% respectively, as provided in Fig. 4.30.

Fig. 4.30 I-V characteristic of cells processed using old KOH-NaOCl and new NaOCl damage etch.

Source: Basu et al. 2013

4.3.3 Omitting the Saw Damage Removal

Considering the time factor in texturization, saw damage etching found to leave no significant improvement in reducing the silicon reflectance if the texturization being prolonged to the certain point. This is being highlighted by Sparber et al. (2003) in their experimental work using conventional KOH-IPA. In the experiment, at least 40 minutes needed to achieved minimum range value of reflectance and the reflectance does not drop drastically after this point as the formation of textured morphology is mostly completed (Fig. 4.31). This agreed by Kim et al. (2013). In their experiment, after KOH saw damage etching, square and inclined plane with exposure to (111) plane was created due to incomplete isotropic etching. As the result, the formation of pyramidal structure by TMAH texturization is faster compared to as-cut and polished wafer and lower reflectance in short texturization duration (comply with Park et al. (2009). Again, for the process long enough for complete formation of pyramidal morphology (in their case is 60 minutes), all wafer either saw damage etched, polished or as-cut condition resulted to near same weighted reflectance of 10 to 11% in

wavelength range of 300 to 1100 nm. The cell with SiN_x layer further decrease the reflectance (lowest 3% in 450 to 650nm wavelengths), thus result to 18.8% efficiency and 80.9% fill factor. Saw damage etching and polishing before texturization hence concluded better to be omitted because of insignificant contribution after allowing the sufficient time for the texturization process.

Fig. 4.31 Weighted reflections of textured wafers, with and without saw damage etching as a function of texturization time.

Source: Sparber et al. 2003

4.4 EFFECT OF POST-TREATMENT

4.4.1 Oxide and Contamination Removal

Solar cell which undergo appropriate cleaning and post-treatment could enhance the passivation and carrier lifetime, one of the example is in case of chemically polished silicon for heterojunction cell by Edwards et al. (2008). After texturization and prior to amorphous silicon deposition, the silicon treated with chemical polish solution composed of HNO_3 - CH_3COOH - HF . Alternatively, high concentration NaOH (28%) could also being used for this purpose which is to thin the sample after the texturing, leaving the surface slightly smoother (reduce stress in intrinsic layer) and remove Si residue (Pirozzi et al. 2001). However, they found it is not favorable because of Na left after the process and did not removed even after amorphous layer deposited,

contributing to lower lifetime. Acidic polishing solution as mentioned before therefore exhibit better result in lifetime, as high as $1074\mu\text{s}$ after longest variable duration (20 seconds), as in Fig. 4.32. As the study, prolonging the treatment costs in higher reflectance; optimum 5 seconds of treatment in chemical polishing proposed for acceptably high lifetime ($899\mu\text{s}$) and reflectance (14.3% at 700nm). The efficiency of cell which is 17.6% was reported.

Fig. 4.32 Minority carrier lifetime as a function of minority carrier concentration for textured n-type c-Si, at different CP etch duration.

Source: Edwards et al. 2008

In different case but still heterojunction cell, oxide removal by HF being discussed by Angermann et al. (2009) on silicon before to amorphous layer deposition. HF is well known its application in oxide removal on silicon surface and not commonly being omitted in all previously discussed experiments, although if not stated. A series of treatment for the best result is demonstrated; starting with RCA cleaning followed by 120 seconds dipping in 1% HF, re-oxidation in $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ at 120°C for 10 minutes, and lastly final 1% HF treatment for 180 seconds. Another point which described to improve the passivation is deposition of amorphous silicon buffer layer before the doped layer and this is independently contribute to better electrical performance with chemically post-treatment as before. Fig. 4.33 shows the

combination of both cleaning and passivation layer. The layer additional layer offer lower defect density at a-Si:H and c-Si interface compared with doped a-Si:H and c-Si interface; resulting to notably increase in open circuit voltage and fill factor of completed cell. Cell with efficiency 16.4% produced with combined effect of proposed chemical treatment and additional layer of intrinsic a-Si:H, an increased in around 3% from reference cell.

Fig. 4.33 The combination of both optimized pre-treatment; standard RCA cleaning, wet chemical smoothing and intrinsic layer.

Source: Angermann et al. 2009

4.4.2 Texture Modification and Porous Silicon

Textured silicon not only removed its oxide in the surface by dipped into the acidic solution but also be rounded and become blunter peak. By this process, residual damage that left on the surface etched out, such as in previously discussed mechanical texturization by Gee et al. (1994) which using HNO_3 -HF solution. The rounding the structure seems like more necessary in direct laser texturing as to remove the debris (Zielke et al. 2012) and excessive melted silicon from the surface (Dobrzanski & Drygala 2008).

Marrero et al. (2009) continue the previously done experiment in Marrero et al. (2007) with additional steps of stain etching before and after the texturization take

place. The formation of porous silicon layer was performed by etching the wafer with 69 wt.% HNO_3 48 wt.% HF aqueous solution (0.1-0.5 concentration). They found that for every stain etching concentration, increasing the duration from 3 to 6 seconds results to lower average reflectance (in wavelength range 300 to 1200nm) but increase in solution concentration not necessarily help reduce the reflectance. Lowest average reflectance obtained (3.16%) with 0.25% HNO_3 -HF stain etch for 6 seconds at room temperature after the Na_2CO_3 - NaHCO_3 texturization. Silicon surface after etched in optimized Na_2CO_3 - NaHCO_3 can be observed its pyramidal structure which caused by etching limitation in (111) direction (Fig. 4.34a), but after stain etched in HNO_3 -HF for a couple seconds the pyramids is softened and losing their tetragonal shape (Fig. 4.34b).

Fig. 4.34 SEM images textured silicon surface. (a) Alkaline textured; and (b) alkaline textured followed by stain etched in acidic solution.

Source: Marrero et al. 2009

However, the porous stain etched silicon after deposited with SiN_x layer as an AR coating, the average reflectance value slightly increase to 3.91% and the cell performance also degraded compare with reference Na_2CO_3 - NaHCO_3 texturization without porous etching (refer to Table 4.10 for comparison). This situation is due to poor metallic contact on textured-porosified surface which caused by inhomogeneity of porous surface, and also result to inadequate deposition of SiN_x layer for passivation because of difficulty on the porous structure compare with flat or alkaline

textured surface. Therefore, stain etching seems not favorable and also alkaline etching for stain etched wafer (pre-etch) need longer texturization duration in order to remove the porous layer before formation of pyramid structure.

Table 4.10 Performance comparison of reference and stain etched samples.

	I_{sc} (A)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)
Reference cell	-3.07	619.0	74.0	14.7
Alkaline textured solar cell	-3.30	611.4	74.9	15.8
Alkaline textured–stain etched solar cell (0.1% HNO ₃ /HF, 6 s)	-3.042	587.4	48.0	8.9
Alkaline textured–stain etched solar cell (0.25% HNO ₃ /HF, 3 s)	-2.934	599.9	57.6	10.5

Source: Marrero et al. 2009

Xiao et al. (2010) study the effect of stain etching using HF-Fe(NO₃)₃ on textured c-Si wafer using conventional KOH-IPA texturization. The wafers after appropriate cleaning contamination and native oxides firstly undergo saw damage etching using 20 wt.% KOH at 80 °C for 2 minutes. The standard texturization using mixture of 3 wt.% KOH and 8 vol.% IPA at 80 °C for 60 minutes was carried out and followed by stain etching using 10 M (M=mol/L) HF and 0.2 M Fe(NO₃)₃ mixture at 50 °C with variation in etching duration from 15 to 60 minutes. The saw damage etching and alkaline texturization manage to obtain acceptable coverage of pyramids texture which sized around 10 μ m (Fig. 4.35a). By stain etching, pits growth is increasing simultaneously with etching duration and after 30 minutes elapsed (Fig. 4.35b), the pyramids texture become blunt then completely collapsed until the end of 60 minutes.

Fig. 4.35 SEM images textured silicon in: (a) KOH-IPA for 60 minutes, and (b) KOH-IPA followed by stain etching for another 30 minutes.

Source: Xiao et al. 2010

The mechanism can be explained by the presence of Fe^{3+} which reduced to Fe^{2+} and oxidized the silicon; later the oxidation of silicon reacts with HF to form H_2SiF_6 which is likely in normal silicon cleaning from oxide. They manage to obtain the lowest weighted reflectance in wavelength range of 400 to 900nm with wafer textured and 30 minutes stain etched which is 4.18%, without ARC (reference KOH-IPA textured wafer used here is 19.99% weighted reflectivity). This is because porous textured silicon is believed to effectively increase short wavelength absorption. However at the same time, one should be alerted that porous silicon texture also leads to lower effective photo-carriers lifetime. The situation might result from greater surface recombination due to porous texture and Fe contamination after long time exposure to $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$. Despite of low reflectance value of textured silicon, no efficiency and fill factor of solar cell reported along with the experiment.

The increase of short wavelength absorption proven by similar concept of nanotexture on micro sized pyramids by Dimitrov & Du (2013). Instead of porous etching, they opted for electroless treatment in acidic aqueous solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and AgNO_3 for 6 minutes followed by etching in followed by etching in $\text{HF}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for another 2 minutes; this process is after typical alkali etching for micro pyramids texturing. Fig. 4.36 provides the fair comparison between reflectance of normal random pyramids structure and similar structure but with nanotexture.

Fig. 4.36 Optical improvement of nanotextured pyramid: (a) evolution of reflectance at different stage, and (b) IQE and reflectance of fabricated solar cell.

Source: Dimitrov & Du 2013

Nanotexture where smaller than the wavelength increased the cell current generation in short wavelength 300-500nm thus an increase in IQE was observed in this range. Both pyramids with or without nanotexture increased the absorbance of weakly absorbed light (red light range) due to lengthened optical path and light trapping by total internal reflection; still better results obtained with the nanotextured pyramids.

4.4.3 Deposited Nanoparticles

Sardana et al. (2014) deposit Ag nanoparticle on the alkaline textured c-Si using RF magnetron sputtering. This is different from any chemical treatment as discussed before, trying to utilizing the role of metal particles on the textured silicon surface. The size of particles increasing with prolonging the deposition time and this heavily differentiates the resulted total reflectance of finished sample. Three time measurement taken into consideration which is 60, 120 and 180 seconds; deposition of Ag nanoparticles by 120 seconds exhibit the lowest reflectance, reduction in around 8% from original reflectance value of textured silicon (14.46% and this near to typical). Textured silicon with Ag nanoparticles after annealing 2 minutes at 300 °C coalescent small particles with large coverage into large particle with small coverage,

necessarily for reducing the parasitic losses caused by Ag while maintaining the desired scattering and reflection reduction. Deposited Ag nanoparticles also modified charge carrier recombination process due to suitability with fingers and busbar on completely fabricated cell, reducing series resistance, improving open circuit voltage and fill factor as in Table 4.11 (same case in Chaoui et al. 2013). For reference purpose, 6.42% cell efficiency for area of 12.24 cm² and 45.65% fill factor was reported, no AR coating being used though.

Table 4.11 Performance of textured cells Ag nanoparticles and after annealed.

Parameters	Bare cell	As-deposited	Annealed 300 °C
V _{oc} (mV)	539	548	548
J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	24.56	22.34	25.62
FF (%)	33.88	42.86	45.65
R _{series} (Ω)	1.24	0.86	0.64
Efficiency (%)	4.49	5.25	6.42

Source: Sardana et al. 2014

4.5 EFFECT OF TEXTURE FEATURE SIZE ON PERFORMANCE

4.5.1 Standard Texture

Fukui et al. (1997) producing cone structure on mc-Si by using REI observe that the surface reflectance of textured silicon decrease with the cone height/width ratio. They are suggesting the best size of cone is 0.2 to 0.4μm height with 0.3 to 0.5μm bottom length; with this size, the uniformity of features is most desired and results to lower reflectance and higher current density compared with smaller one. The short circuit current which resulted from cone size is related as in Fig. 4.37. However if aspect ratio is too high which is indicating deep structure, it will lead to the large saturation current and decreasing the performance.

Fig. 4.37 Influence of the cone size textured by RIE.

Source: Fukui et al. 1997

Features less than $1\mu\text{m}$ is not commonly can be obtained from chemical wet etching which is detailed in previous subchapter due to simplicity in the process itself compared to REI. Pyramids after immersion of c-Si into texturing bath with medium size around $5\mu\text{m}$ as reported by Hayashi et al. (2006) should be the optimum for solar cell purpose. In their work, worth to mention that the spherical silicon solar cell being fabricated and due to the texturization, as high as 13% improvement in short circuit current density was gained compared to the cell without textured surface; smaller texture size ($1\mu\text{m}$) at the meanwhile exhibit increase in 9%. Beside the reflectance measurement which justifies the reduction in optical losses, the size of pyramids also influences the cell during the fabrication. As shown in Fig. 4.38, smaller pyramids tend to have many crystal defects on the top due to more fragile than larger pyramids and result to increase in shunt path. Furthermore, smaller pyramid of $1\mu\text{m}$ will have deeper emitter, yielding to slightly lower open circuit voltage compared with $5\mu\text{m}$ pyramids which eventually affect the fill factor and overall cell performance. The comparison of pyramids size upon performance is provided in Table 4.12.

Fig. 4.38 Schematic of crystal defects induced in cell fabrication for the pyramids size of: (a) 1 μm , and (b) 5 μm .

Source: Hayashi et al. 2006

Table 4.12 Performance of textured and non textured spherical Si solar cell.

Sample	J_{sc} (mA/cm^2)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)
Without texturing	29.6	580	67.6	11.6
With 1 μm pyramids	32.1	577	65.2	12.1
With 5 μm pyramids	33.5	592	61.8	12.2

Source: Hayashi et al. 2006

The reflectance of on the silicon surface relate very much with short circuit current density while another cell efficiency indicator, which is minority carrier lifetime is deciding the fill factor and open circuit voltage of the cell. Jeong et al. (2009) relate the lifetime with textured pyramids size with produced by conventional NaOH-IPA texturization. In their case, heterojunction solar cell was fabricated with amorphous silicon as passivation layer. Three range of pyramids size being divided for comparison; small (1-3 μm), medium (3-5 μm) and large (5-7 μm). The medium size pyramids exhibit longest lifetime among them, followed by large and then small. The reason why small pyramids could not perform very well related with its texturization process; short texturing duration insufficiently removes the micro crack and damage caused by saw dicing. Consequently, fill factor lowered due to poorer open circuit voltage. In case of large features, the presence of pyramids with high peak made the

deposited passivation layer more at the valley; it is also not preferred. The author highlighted the need of considering electrical characteristic (minority carrier lifetime) as well as optical characteristic, because of in the experiment all three of stated pyramids size result to comparable reflectance in wavelength of 300 to 1000nm. Actually, the best fill factor based on Fig. 4.39 is achieved between 1.5-3.2 μm which is middle between defined small and medium feature size.

Fig. 4.39 IV curve which depends on textured pyramid height.

Source: Jeong et al. 2009

4.5.2 Other Type of Texture

Yoshinaga et al. (2013) produce the texture of silicon for solar cell purpose by nanoimprinting the ZrO_2 and ZnO ; classified as another type of surface modification method without etching or physically damage the silicon. Exceptionally high efficiency actually being obtained by this kind of method which is as high as 22.9% for ZrO_2 while 20.9% for ZnO . The ZrO_2 has higher refractive index and wider bandgap than ZnO , contributing to advantages in cell efficiency. For this kind of texture, feature size of 0.25 μm is the optimum for both nanoimprinted ZrO_2 and ZnO , resulting to the best short circuit current density and efficiency (Fig. 4.40a). The AR coating layer, SiN optimally with refractive index of 3.0 is to best suit with the nanoimprinted structures regardless of its thickness, as being experimentally proved in Fig. 4.40(b) with index of 2.0 for comparison. While the rich Si in SiN passivation

layer can suppress the reflectance, thickening this layer also make the reflectance slightly higher compared with thinner one, implying the nanoimprinted material actually having passivation effect as pointed out by the author.

Fig. 4.40 The relation of cell efficiency with: (a) ZrO₂ and ZnO feature sizes, and (b) refractive index and thickness.

Source: Yoshinaga et al 2013

Instead of conventionally textured using KOH, Chen et al. (2011) deposit the micro-spherical texture (MST) structure on the silicon surface by nozzle spray. The process of producing the structure which incorporating ITO and micro-spherical structure briefly described by Fig. 4.41 below, consisting 4 key steps which is; deposition of ITO on planar silicon surface, nozzle spray of 4 μm sized silica particles and then spin-on-glass film coating to produce final omnidirection AR coating structure.

Fig. 4.41 Key process in depositing omnidirectional AR coating structure.

Source: Chen et al. 2011

The light if fall on different positions and perpendicularly to the pyramids which being obtained by chemical wet etching (or similar features by RIE and etc) will slightly worsen in desired reflection due to the decrease of multi reflection to neighboring structure, but not in case of this ITO incorporated micro-spherical structure. At incident angle of 60°, the difference in efficiency as high as 13.5% compared with reference KOH textured cell was measured, while at normal incident the difference is 7.4%. This is because the hemispherical structure with the plano-convex shape is less sensitive to the incident angle of light, thus demonstrating its capability of omnidirectional anti reflection. Table 4.13 compares the performance of fabricated cells (ITO with MST) with conventional cell with SiN_x and ITO as the AR coating. As high as 18.01% efficiency obtained with ITO + MST cell with prior HCl pretreatment due to smoothing of Si-ITO interface.

Table 4.13 Performance comparison of cell with coating configurations.

	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)
KOH cell + SiN _x AR coating	36.1	618	74.6	16.64
KOH cell + ITO AR coating	35.9	612	77.5	17.03
ITO + MST w/o HCl treatment	36.6	616	78.5	17.69
ITO + MST with HCl treatment	37.3	618	78.1	18.01

Source: Chen et al. 2011

Not only limited to that, silicon texture in form of nanowire also taken into the consideration. The example would be article by He et al. (2012), working on nanowires produced on 2.2 μ m thick epitaxial silicon grown on the n-type silicon by electroless chemical etching in HF-AgNO₃ with variation in nanowires size. Later, it is being coated by 3,4-ethylene-dioxythiophene:polystyrenesulfonate (PEDOT:PSS), shown schematically in Fig. 4.42(a) and under SEM magnification in Fig. 4.42(b).

Fig. 4.42 SiNWs/PEDOT hybrid cell: (a) Schematic during fabrication, and (b) SEM image of $0.35\mu\text{m}$ nanowire coated with PEDOT layer.

Source: He et al. 2012

Continuous canopy of PEDOT formed on $0.3\mu\text{m}$ length nanowires which initially before the deposition closely packed and vertically aligned; non-uniformity was observed in nanowires up to $1.5\mu\text{m}$ and also non-uniform surface contour after PEDOT deposition. In term of complete fabricated cell performance from the sample, $0.3\mu\text{m}$ length nanowires result to slightly higher short circuit current density, open circuit voltage, fill factor, and efficiency compared to planar surface and larger size of nanowires. Poorer performance of larger nanowires contributed from lower shunt resistance and higher recombination rate in spite of offering enhancement in light trapping. The only $2.2\mu\text{m}$ thick absorber layer with optimum nanowires size demonstrate high fill factor (71.9%) and 5.6% efficiency, potentially for low cost yet efficient Si/organic based hybrid cells.

However, while the desired texture proven lowered the R_s , the short circuit current density not necessarily increased due to non-simple proportionality relationship (Kwon et al 2009). The side effects of textured surface need to be considered to avoid further necessity and performance drop.

4.6 SIDE EFFECT OF TEXTURIZATION

4.6.1 Carrier Losses

The textured surface on crystalline silicon which proven enhance light trapping ability as crucial factor in determining cell efficiency however need to consider and cope with some drawbacks that will be discussed. In most cases, for chemical wet etching and physical dry texturing method, proper cleaning and treatment such as RCA method and HF dipping needed to ensure oxides being removed from the surface before proceed to next stage in cell fabrication. Especially for silicon sample which being textured in conventional KOH or NaOH solution, again would like to highlight that the contamination due to potassium or sodium left after the process need to acceptably deal with it otherwise will leave detrimental effect in desired application, in electronics or specifically solar cell. The silicon surface which containing ion residue if being re-oxidized, the ion contamination will be removed along with oxide after being dipped into HF solution (Vazsonyi et al. 1999).

Large surface area after texturization as known (around 1.73 times larger) will increase surface recombination velocity and shorten the lifetime (Bachtouli et al. 2012); side effects of defects on the surface can be reduced by saturating the dangling bond on exposed surface. This can be achieved by PECVD method, depositing the passivation layer such as a-Si:H layer on the top of textured surface; how the textured surface morphology effect the performance of the plasma passivation was studied by Mehrabian et al. (2013) by simulation. The hydrogen ions during the actual process distributed to the silicon surface in order to terminate the dangling bond modeled in the way of taking the electric field of the textured silicon microstructure into the consideration. Flat surface indicate the higher degree of uniformity in hydrogen ions coverage compared to the textured surface, fortunately it was not severely affecting the final output of surface passivation as the dangling bond saturation only slightly lower in the textured surface and can be ignored if further optimization in plasma process condition is done. AR coating also serves the similar purpose; SiN_x or $\text{SiO}_2/\text{SiN}_x$ double layers (Schmidt et al. 2001), or also a-Si:H/ SiN_x :H double layers (Li et al. 2011).

4.6.2 Mechanical Strength

One of advantages of texturing besides optical and electrical consideration would be improvement in mechanical strength in silicon sample as reported by Stefancich et al. (2001). The stress test was conducted in cantilever configuration. They found that, by wet chemical texturization c-Si either acidic (HF-HNO₃-CH₃COOH) or alkaline (NaOH) solution, the maximum elongation and sustainable load is higher compared with reference sample after saw dicing. The comparative parameter of maximum tension on the top of cantilever surface ($\sigma = 6Fd/WH^2$) where F is the collapse load, d is the distance of the holder from the force application point, W is the sample width and H for its thickness between the three sample (as sawn, basic alkaline and acidic texturing) is shown in Fig. 4.43.

Fig. 4.43 Measured maximum stress vs relative frequency of critical load occurrence for differently textured silicon sample.

Source: Stefancich et al. 2001

Taking the thinning factor of silicon after being textured compared with as-sawed sample into consideration, estimated improvement in toughness as high as 150% for alkaline etching and 250% for acidic etching obtained relative to original sample. This is because, might due to damages in on the silicon after ingot sawing severely affect the ultimate material toughness, limiting the mechanical resistance by its defect.

4.6.3 Effect Upon and After Cell Fabrication

4.6.3.a Uneven Metal Contact

Structures should not larger than $10\mu\text{m}$ in order to avoid interference with sequenced cell processing step (Iencinella et al. 2005). According to Gangopadhyay et al. (2006), less sharp pyramids texture (chemical wet etching) lead to uniform metal coverage on front grid lines after screen printing and firing, proven under SEM observation and as the result, more desired cell efficiency and fill factor achieved. In the previously discussed article by Nakamura et al. (2013) which explaining about the pyramidal formation of chemical wet etching, large texture that obtained using high concentration of KOH and pre-described mechanism result to highest efficiency (18%) and fill factor (80%) after completely fabricated as a working solar cell with presence of SiN_x as the ARC. Slightly lower fill factor in smaller texture might caused by lack of uniformity and inhomogeneous; this claim was strengthen by the electrophotoluminescence (EL) images as shown in Fig. 4.44.

Fig. 4.44 EL images of finish fabricated solar cell using wafer with:
(a) Large texture, and (b) small texture after the etching.

Source: Nakamura et al. 2013

The unevenness of front finger contact more likely occur in smaller textured morphology of silicon wafer and consequently the shunt resistance of cell being raised. Another thing that include in consideration is the presence of thick damaged

layer at the top and bottom of texture which interfacing with SiN_x layer as the size of texture smaller. The damaged layer might be induced by PECVD and should be minimized to obtain better and desired cell efficiency.

Even though larger structure proven to have lower value of light reflection, unfortunately it also increase surface unevenness and thus originate the worse Ag-Si contact in the bottom of nanohilllock as reported by Zhong et al. (2013). In the experiment, mc-Si wafer was textured by using REI and later optimized its etching parameter in which average reflectance significantly lower compared with acid textured solar cell. However, in term of cell efficiency, proposed method was slightly lower than the efficiency of acid textured cell and poorer fill factor as indicated in Fig. 4.45 (C3 textured is optimized parameters).

Fig. 4.45 I-V characteristic of cells textured with REI parameter C3 and acid textured.

Source: Zhong et al. 2013

The investigation under SEM as shown in Fig. 4.46 reveals that n-rich layer remaining in the bottom valley of the nanostructures, and also Ag particles precipitated on it.

Fig. 4.46 Cross-sectional SEM images of Ag-Si contact of the solar cells:
(a) Optimized RIE, and (b) acid textured silicon.

Source: Zhong et al. 2013

There were pores left due to reaction between AgO_2 and SiN_x . The remaining n-rich layer between Ag-Si with high contact resistance contributes to bad current transmission, while the fine distribution of Ag crystallites result to low contact resistance because of allowing current transportation via a nearly metal-semiconductor contact.

4.6.3.b Junction Breakdown

Etch pits formed due to wet chemical etching which selectively etch the grain boundaries and dislocation on the surface contribute to defect-induced breakdown. Kwopil et al. (2012) for this study purpose produces three different levels of texture on mc-Si; strong texture, weak texture and almost flat surface after damage layer removal. Strong texture for mc-Si being obtained by acidic texturization using $\text{HF-HNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ which result to rough surface with deep etch pits ($2\text{-}3\mu\text{m}$) while for the weak texture, high concentration $\text{HF-HNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O-CH}_3\text{COOH}$ etching leaves the surface with shallower etch pits ($1\text{-}2\mu\text{m}$) due to high etching rate isotropically.

The breakdown voltage of certain mc-Si solar cell influenced by two main factors; they are silicon surface morphology and recombination activity. More rough the surface, lower defect-induced breakdown voltage will be. Also, region on the

surface which have higher recombination activity break down at lower reverse voltage; high recombination active defect correlate with deep of pits and point where crystal defect is located is often selectively etched, contributed from trapped impurities inside it during the crystallization. Fig. 4.47 shows the distribution of breakdown voltage of strongly and weakly textured mc-Si solar cell and the green dotted circle highlighting the area with high recombination; lower reverse voltage for breakdown set for deeper etch pit. Surface texturing found to be ‘hardens’ the local defect-induced breakdown with steep increase of reversed current compared with smoother surface of damage removed sample in I-V curve. Depth of etching has an impact on the local emitter formation; deeper pits means that less phosphosilicate glass was deposited and leave the impact on the space charge region around the tip.

Fig. 4.47 Maps of measured breakdown voltage measured on cells that are:

(a) Strongly textured, and (b) weakly textured.

Source: Kwapil et al. 2012

For the comparison between different level of texture; damage etch, weak texture, and strong texture, in Fig. 4.48, the approximate local breakdown voltage on nine different solar cells is plotted against the local etch pit depth.

Fig. 4.48 Local breakdown voltage vs depth of the etch pits measured at defect induced breakdown regions of neighboring solar cells.

Source: Kwapil et al. 2012

Another type of breakdown in mc-Si related with texturization is avalanche breakdown, second threat next to defect-induced breakdown. According to Bauer et al. (2012), this problem more pronounced in alkali textured mc-Si compared with acid; this is due to acid etch isotropically while selectivity etch of alkali leave the slightly different curvature shape. If the shape is not perfectly spherical (as indicated in Fig. 4.49), the absolute breakdown voltage then is higher.

Fig. 4.49 Curvature radius of p-n junction which follows the textured surface.

Source: Bauer et al. 2012

4.7 THIN FILM: TCO TEXTURIZATION

The light trapping mechanism thin film amorphous silicon (a-Si) is similar to the conventional bulk Si cell, except the advantages of direct bandgap semiconductor intrinsically require less material (100nm thick is adequate) in order to absorb fractions of sunlight compared with indirect bandgap of bulk c-Si (Andreani et al. 2012; Bozzola et al. 2012). Incident light will go through the cell via transparent surface to the textured surface morphology and being refracted into intrinsic layer. Later, travelling light is reflected by rear surface to the front surface and some of them will either reflected back by total internal reflection and being absorbed or losses to outer layer (Fig. 4.50). There were two main configurations in cell; n-i-p and p-i-n where the concept applied to both but no doubt they will difference in certain ways that will covered later on.

Fig. 4.50 The concept of light trapping in thin film silicon solar cell.

Source: Muller et al. 2004

In p-i-n cell configuration, the first layer start with glass, followed by transparent conducting oxide (TCO) deposition and texturing of that particular TCO to obtain uneven surface morphology. The p-type of amorphous silicon deposited on the textured surface and followed by intrinsic, n-type, and metal back reflector. This was considered very simple structure; more complicated can be achieve by depositing various additional layer that specifically to improve overall cell performance (tandem cell). While in case of n-i-p cell configuration, the substrate of deposition start with metal back reflector which is completely reverse version of p-i-n cell. So that, the

metal being textured to produce desired microstructure on the surface and the unevenness will be forwarded to next layer of n-type, intrinsic, p-type, and AR coating layer, just like the role of textured TCO as before. The significant difference of how the textured surface will affect the cell performance lies in role of front and rear texture of that particular cell.

4.7.1 Texturing Method and Type of TCO

Transparent conducting oxide very important in fabricating thin film silicon solar cell, as its name suggest, it provide transparent feature that allow photon to be transmitted into the active layer while also conducting the electrical charge to be connected to external circuitry. There were several thumb rules in selecting the TCO material, one of them stated that the need for low sheet resistance which less than 10-15 Ω /sq. TCO also need to have low light absorption in visible range favorably less than 5%. The absorbance of light for current generation however varies from different type of silicon; for amorphous silicon (a-Si) the transparency requirement may ranged from 400 to 750nm while for microcrystalline silicon (μ c-Si), the transparency ought up to near infrared region 1100nm (Muller et al. 2004). Another main criterion in selecting TCO would be its ability to scatter the light which can be achieve by surface modification to produce suitable texture for this purpose. Haze value in which indicating the light scattering of TCO preferably need to be high, for example more than 5% (Hegedus & Buchanan 1996).

Commonly used TCO nowadays which available in the market would be Asahi U glass, or basically textured fluorine doped SnO_2 ($\text{SnO}_2:\text{F}$). However, one of remarkable limitation of this material is its oxidation by exposure to radical hydrogen during a-Si:H deposition as mostly discussed and circulated in various literatures which not included here. Alternatively Al doped ZnO ($\text{ZnO}:\text{Al}$ or AZO) also attract much attention due some advantages that its offer; for example of feasible in preparation and bypass the limitation of oxidization by exposure to radical hydrogen as mentioned before. The simple preparation of AZO demonstrated by Sobajima et al. (2007) using sol-gel method, followed by spin coating on the glass substrate and later annealing in the furnace. By this method, preferential (002) peak of hexagonal ZnO

managed to be obtained, both in before and after the rapid thermal annealing. The annealing process after spin coating of film is required as initial layer have resistivity as high as 25 Ωm ; the resistivity inversely proportional to annealing temperature. At 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ annealing, acceptable low 1.4×10^{-2} Ωcm resistance obtained. In fact, in the experiment, higher temperature of annealing not only decreases the resistivity of AZO but also increases the carrier concentration and carrier mobility. The improvement can further being achieved if spin coat is done on the textured glass surface, leaving the surface of AZO rough, enhancing the light trapping and photocurrent generation. The roughness can even higher than conventional $\text{SnO}_2\text{:F}$, but also depending on the substrate.

ZnO:Al film was prepared by Berginski et al. (2007) on the Corning 1737 glass for thin film solar $\mu\text{-Si:H}$ cell by using RF magnetron sputtering. In the article, they reported the parameter during the process that affecting the performance of TCO and solar cell; they are:

- i. Target alumina (Al_2O_3) concentration in which directly influencing the doping level of Al in ZnO.
- ii. Substrate temperature during the RF magnetron sputtering.

There are three types of surface condition for deposited ZnO:Al after wet etching in diluted HF acid. Type II said to be most desired compared with I and III due to uniform coverage of crater-like structure with diameter ranging from 1 to $3\mu\text{m}$ and depth of 150 to 400nm (Fig. 4.51a). The recipe of obtained type II surface of ZnO:Al suggested to be 0.5 to 1.0 wt.% of alumina as the target of sputtering with combination of 360 to 410 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ substrate temperature during the deposition. The schematic distribution of types of ZnO:Al is provided in Fig. 4.51(b). For the optimized type II surface of ZnO:Al, the haze value is up to 40% at $1\mu\text{m}$ wavelength. The light trapping ability is further justified with improvement in QE in which contributed from better photogeneration in NIR wavelength (due to the structure which allowing more generation by $\mu\text{-Si}$), and not to mention also contributed from better electrical properties of ZnO:Al itself. Further improvement then lies in dealing with limitation in parasitic absorption losses at rear surface by back reflector.

Fig. 4.51 Three surface types of ZnO:Al (post etch) which obtained: (a) AFM images with features size comparison, and (b) region of each types can be obtained.

Source: Bergenski et al. 2007

Kang et al. (2010) relate the deposition temperature of ZnO:Al using DC magnetron sputtering with the deposition rate and etching rate (after deposition finished) in the 0.5% diluted HCl. Increasing in the substrate temperature decrease both the deposition and post etching rate, indicating the more dense and compact structure of growth ZnO:Al film. More dense and compact ZnO:Al prone to be insufficient texturing in acidic solution compared with less dense sample if the texturing parameter is similar, leading to less desired optical properties. At the mean time, the electrical resistivity also steadily decreased due to increase film crystallinity at higher deposition temperature. Increasing Al content in higher deposition temperature increase the refractive index of film might because more Al available functioning as scattering centers. In term of haze value however, if compared with room temperature substrate (25°C), 200 °C deposition temperature result to higher haze (70% at 550nm and 36% at 800nm) but 400 °C far lower from both (25 and 200 °C), although texturing was completed after considering the low etch rate as stated before. With acceptable optoelectronic properties which desired as TCO, they suggest for 200 °C substrate temperature for deposition; with target alumina concentration of they used 2 wt.%, it comply with recommendation based on schematic distribution of type II surface by previously discussed Bergenski et al. (2007). The view of structures size is in Fig. 4.52.

Fig. 4.52 View of Zn:Al films deposited at 200 °C: (a) Cross section, and (b) tilted.

Source: Kang et al. 2010

The effect of etching duration explored by Wang et al. (2013), applied on the deposited DC magnetron sputtering of Al-Y codoped ZnO (AZOY). In the experiment, diluted acidic solution of H_3PO_4 was used with variation in etching time from 0 to 120 seconds. Deposited AZOY at 250 °C (as they claimed to have best crystalline quality) initially have the lowest electrical resistivity, highest carrier mobility and also highest carrier concentration compared with etched film. Increasing in etching duration shift the surface morphology from smooth to lunar landscape-like; after 120 seconds elapsed, craters with around 2 μ m obtained. As the haze value increase with prolonging the etching duration, more light to be scattered into the cell. In NIR region in which 900 to 1100nm wavelength, increase of etching duration always improve the quantum efficiency. This is because of light transmission of AZOY in the NIR increased with increased in etching time, allowing more base layer absorption for current generation. However for the case of 120 seconds immersion in the H_3PO_4 , excess etching which leave the surface with large characteristic lateral features of flat crater degraded the photovoltaic properties of the solar cell.

Texturing the deposited AZO using magnetron sputtering not only limited by wet etching using acid, but also more sophisticated method for example inductively coupled plasma (ICP) in which presented by Jeong et al. (2008). This kind of method which is a part of reactive ion etching (REI) subject, avoid the problem of lateral etch and temperature depended etch rate of acidic solution. The roughness of the surface

can be controlled by varying two important parameters in the process; gas ratio and RF chuck power as described in Fig. 4.53 which taken from original article.

Fig. 4.53 The corresponding surface roughness of AZO in regard to:

(a) Cl₂/Ar etching gas ratio, and (b) RF chuck power.

Source: Jeong et al. 2008

The textured AZO by this method (300W and gas ratio of 2) resulted to improvement in quantum efficiency of fabricated cell for broad wavelength ranging from 490 to 950nm compared with cell which deposited on flat magnetron sputtered AZO. Also, the increase in short circuit current density obtained from 11.2 to 15.8 mA/cm² and overall consideration pointed that this method is very suitable in case of alternative for wet etching is required.

4.7.2 Influence of Textured Front Side TCO

Textured TCO plays important role in determining the surface morphology of next layer as they are deposited directly on top of it. The growth of silicon active layer by thin film deposition on the substrate elaborated by Jovanov et al. (2013) in their experiment on the amorphous silicon with Asahi U (SnO₂) and etched ZnO as the TCO. For this purpose, the term of realistic approximation was introduced its growth indicated in Fig. 4.54(b), contrast with standard growth approximation Fig. 4.54(a).

Fig. 4.54 The formation of a-Si on substrate: (a) direction in normal to the substrate, and (b) direction in normal to the local surface (realistic).

Source: Jovanov et al. 2013

The roughness of final rear surface was the function of the silicon diode thicknesses, for both Asahi U and ZnO; if the textured surface feature size of the substrate is comparable with the thickness of the deposited a-Si (p, i, and n layer), then the morphology of rear surface will be distinctly different from the front surface. Otherwise, if the front surface feature is larger than the thickness of deposited a-Si, the rear surface will be smaller in difference. Controllable texture of etched ZnO which generally in larger size (crater-like feature) compared with Asahi U; makes them more valid in second case where front surface feature is larger than the thickness of deposited layer. In multicrystalline silicon thin film cell deposited by electron beam, larger crystal of silicon grown on rough surface of TCO compared with smooth surface (Becker et al. 2011).

In different situation, Zhang et al. (2014) shift the texturing from TCO to the texturing of glass instead. The process to obtain textured glass require ZnO:Al etching mask before being exposed to etching ion beam. After that, again ZnO:Al being utilized by sputtered on the textured glass as the TCO (Fig. 4.55). They measured the roughness of texture glass where it was 104nm. After 250nm thick ZnO:Al layer deposited on it, the measured ZnO:Al roughness was 105.5nm which almost exact value of underlying glass substrate, indicating the growth of ZnO:Al conformal to the glass substrate regardless deposition of thick layer.

Fig. 4.55 Textured glass substrate before and after ZnO:Al deposition.

Source: Zhang et al. 2014

The haze value depends on many factors such as type of TCO material, size of textured microstructure on it, features shape, and thickness as we learn from comparison which being made by Hegedus & Buchanan (1996) in which between SnO₂ and ZnO; detailed physical properties of each of them is in Table 4.14.

Table 4.14 List of TCOs and their physical characteristics.

TCO Label (matl:haze)	Thickness (μm)	Feature Size (μm)	Feature Shape
SnO ₂ :14%, APCVD	1.0	0.6	Angular grains.
SnO ₂ :7%, APCVD	0.8	0.6	Well formed faceted angular grains.
SnO ₂ :2%, APCVD	0.7	0.3	Bi-modal size, some well formed grains.
SnO ₂ :1%, APCVD	0.4	0.2	Small grains, some rounded, some well formed.
ZnO:5%, LPCVD	1.5	0.4	Angular grains.
ZnO:5%, LPCVD	1.6	0.5	Well formed faceted angular grains.
ZnO: 6%, APCVD	1.2	0.3	Small rounded grains.

Source: Hegedus & Buchanan 1996

Start with SnO₂, increasing its haze value from 1% up to 7% lead to increase in short circuit current density (up to 13.2 mA/cm²) due to decrease in short wavelength reflection at front surface. The 7% haze SnO₂ composed of 0.6 μm well formed faceted angular grains, deposited by atmospheric pressure CVD (APCVD). However, no improvement obtained in short circuit current density by increasing its

haze value up to 14% (0.6 μm angular grains features also by APCVD) except slightly higher open circuit voltage which lead to slightly better fill factor. ZnO in other hand result to higher short circuit current density at only 5% haze (13.5 mA/cm²) but lower fill factor. The surface composed of 0.4 μm angular grains resulted from low pressure CVD (LPCVD) process. The optical transparency of TCO is closely related with its electrical conductivity where in case of thin TCO being used, lower light absorption actually observed but often increases its sheet resistance. Besides its role in enhancing light trapping by the textured surface which similar in case of conventional silicon cell, optimization also should consider good balance between good electrical and optical properties with respect to each other (Muller et al. 2004). Thick layer of 250nm ZnO:Al as previously by Zhang et al. (2014) also proven worsen in trapping near infrared range and later reduced its thickness to 60nm.

Ernes et al. (2014) in order to study about effect of front surface texture, modify the texture size based on initial textured surface morphology of ZnO:Al as shown in Fig. 4.56. The modification is based on ratio from reference texture size in term of stretching or compressing in height (z axis) f_z and lateral (x and y axis) f_{xy} . The crater-like structure has global optimum radius at 1.5 μm . Without any modification, the value of f_z and f_{xy} is equivalent to 1.

Fig. 4.56 Reference texture used for simulations as obtained by AFM.

Source: Ernes et al. 2014

The absorption of initial f_z and f_{xy} taken as 1 for the reference. According to Table 4.15, in simplified single junction cell, the average total absorption of ZnO:Al can be increased by compressing the texture in lateral direction with f_{xy} reduced to 0.6 where as high as 15.4% improvement in light absorption from initial value obtained. Stretching the texture lowered the absorption, worst obtained is at $f_{xy} = 2$ (double from original) where reduction in 13.9% from reference value. By increase the height of texture by f_z to 2, improvement in absorption by 6.5% obtained. When the height reduced by half ($f_z = 0.5$), worst absorption obtained which is 10.2% reduction from reference value.

Table 4.15 Relative in absorption based on lateral and height modification.

f_{xy}	Δ_{Abs}	f_z	Δ_{Abs}
0.5	13.7%	0.5	-10.2%
0.6	15.4%	1.0	0%
0.7	11.5%	1.1	1.6%
0.8	7.2%	1.2	3.5%
0.9	3.3%	1.3	4.9%
1.0	0%	1.4	6.4%
1.5	-12.5%	1.5	5.2%
2.0	-13.9%	2.0	6.5%
		2.5	6.3%
		3.0	5.2%

Source: Ernes et al. 2014

4.7.3 Effect of Rear Texture

Front surface roughness need to be combined with highly reflective back contact surface in order to optimize the cell efficiency. While the deposition of back layer reflector adapt the roughness of front surface texture due to direct deposition is good for enhancing scattering (p-i-n configuration), however it also lead to additional light absorption in rough metal. Commonly used Al and Ag as metal back reflector can be improve by using double layer with additional of TCO; for example ZnOAl.

According to Muller et al. (2004), when the need for rough textured Ag or Al cannot be avoided but still the absorption losses is substantial, a dielectric back reflector could be the solution. In simplest and cheapest manner, it could be achieved by using white mat painting; or by more sophisticated way, it could be for example by applying one dimensional photonic crystal and at the same time possible to be designed for high omnidirectional reflectivity for wide spectral range.

Sai & Kondo (2009) list down three beneficial effect of improved back surface reflector structure, they are: Increased reflectivity of back surface reflector, enhance effectiveness of front side light scattering, and enhance effectiveness of rear side light scattering. They have worked on fabricating n-i-p type $\mu\text{c-Si:H}$ by using Al as substrate. The Al being textured using anodic oxidation process and found that the best microstructure size to be around $1\mu\text{m}$ for $1\mu\text{m}$ thick $\mu\text{c-Si:H}$ cell (more than $1.2\mu\text{m}$ uniform feature size so far cannot be achieved by anodic oxidation as proposed). More than 90% of visible light reflected diffusely for microstructure larger than $0.9\mu\text{m}$ due to increased the optical path length in thin layer of $\mu\text{c-Si:H}$.

Proper comparison between effects of rear textured surface between p-i-n and n-i-p cell configuration later being made by the same authors in sequenced article reported; Sai & Kondo (2010). For the p-i-n (rear texture not intentionally controlled) and n-i-p cell configuration, the type of contribution can be distinguished by more significant EQE improvement in NIR region by rear surface texture in n-i-p compared with p-i-n cell. This is due to small critical angle of total internal reflection at the front side of the n-i-p cell. The schematic of both cells configuration shown in Fig. 4.57 for better understanding.

Fig. 4.57 Schematic of thin film cell in which have both rear and front texture surface: (a) n-i-p, and (b) p-i-n configuration.

Source: Sai et al. 2010

The results Sai & Kondo (2010) in Fig. 4.58 strongly related and comply in data presented by Sai et al (2010). Rear textured surface (Al) in p-i-n configuration lead to photon absorption loss in NIR region, agreed with as per discussed before by Muller et al. (2004). The same problem found in n-i-p but less pronounced, indicating the rear texture surface actually bring advantage and disadvantage as a bundle; proven effectively elongating optical light path but also increased absorption loss due to reduced reflectivity (at rear surface) in both cell configuration.

Fig. 4.58 EQE and absorbed spectra with/without rear texture: (a) p-i-n, and (b) n-i-p.

Source: Sai & Kondo 2010

Matsui et al. (2002) fabricated the n-i-p type polycrystalline silicon thin film solar cell using different roughness of substrate; smooth and textured. For the smooth surface, ZnO/Ag double layer deposited on the glass ($\sigma_{\text{rms}}=26\text{nm}$) while for the textured one, ZnO/Ag deposited on textured SnO₂ which available from Asahi Glass Company ($\sigma_{\text{rms}}=38\text{--}55\text{nm}$). Increasing the roughness from 26–55nm actually lowering the reflectance significantly in range of 600nm and above but in term of quantum efficiency, increasing the roughness not always improve the efficiency. This poor performance was caused by deterioration in poly-Si (220) preferential growth at high value of substrate roughness.

The similar conclusion also drawn by Muhida et al. (2013) which worked on poly-Si cell with n-i-p configuration on the substrate of SnO₂ with different surface roughness (Asahi Glass Company). The effect of substrate roughness upon cell performance indicators is shown in Fig. 4.59. In regard with the structural change of deteriorated crystallinity, the layer of poly-Si on the highly textured SnO₂ exhibits n-type character; it decrease the photosensitivity and increase carrier recombination rate in which ultimately lead to poor cell performance.

Fig. 4.59 Relationship between RMS roughness of substrate with:
(a) J_{sc} , and (b) V_{oc} of 2.5 μm thick poly-Si cell.

Source: Muhida et al. 2013

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION

5.1 LESSON LEARNED

There are several things that need to re-emphasize in this chapter based on the literature study in previous. There are 5 main R&D aspects to be highlighted in Si solar cell texturization: understanding mechanism of optical loss reduction, methods of texturization, desired textured feature, side effect of texturization and texture compatibility with other optical enhancement. The desired criteria for textured Si surface were summarized in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 Criteria of desired textured Si surface.

Desired characteristic	
Optimum feature size	The optimum feature size is ranged from 0.1–10 μ m. Submicron structures were not likely to be achieved by low cost chemical etching and mechanical grooving.
High coverage, homogeneity and uniformity	Optimum feature size itself could not lower the Si reflectivity without emphasize on feature coverage, homogeneity and uniformity (near 100% coverage). Keys are randomization of structures, not too big feature, and capability of process to texture uniformly across the Si surface.
High surface roughness	High RMS value of surface roughness is product of both mentioned criteria above; highest surface roughness across the textured Si result to lowest reflectivity.

Four types of physical dry method evaluated in previous chapter. The advantages and disadvantages of every method provided in Table 5.2; a result from the essences of literature study conducted.

Table 5.2 Remarks on advantages and disadvantages of physical method.

	Advantage	Disadvantage
Mechanical	Low cost (could be lowest), high texturing rate, suitable for both c-Si and mc-Si	Larger feature size compared with other method (10-100 μ m or larger), no randomization in features
REI	Capable producing small structures in submicron range (<1 μ m), high feature uniformity, suitable for both c-Si and mc-Si	Sometimes need chemical post-treatment to smoothen sharp cone texture (to avoid side effect)
Gas etching	Gas etch the Si without the plasma, applicable to both c-Si and mc-Si	Isotropic etching for c-Si; not as selective as chemical etching (alkali texturing)
Laser ablation	Accuracy of laser, more flexible (depends on setup), applicable to both c-Si and mc-Si	Si necessary to be treated with chemical after texturing, higher level of sophistication

While for the chemical method, the texturing process is more alterable or adjustable compared with basic physical process due to modification in etchant and other process parameter. Table 5.3 listed the known recipes of alkali wet texturing for c-Si which able to obtain desired results. By either way of texturization (physical or chemical), there were several limitation as thoroughly discussed in chapter IV and summarized in Table 5.4. Finally in Table 5.5, the effects of texturization on solar cell performance were fairly compared for a complete evaluation.

Table 5.3 Recipes of alkali texturing and their capability to texture c-Si.

Reference	Chemical	Optimum Mixture	Temp.	Time	Reflectance	Remark
Park et al. (2009)	KOH	45% KOH+IPA+DIW in ratio 1:6:55	80 °C	30 min	10.7% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.1\mu\text{m}}$	Pre-treatment in HF and KOH SDE. Same parameter KOH+TBA with R=11.92%
Chu et al. (2009)		1 wt% KOH	90 °C	20 min	15.1% at $\lambda_{0.4-1.1\mu\text{m}}$	Pre-treatment in 10% HF; using 1mm separation and 2mm ² opening metal grid
Sparber et al. (2013)		3 wt% KOH + 5 vol% IPA	80 °C	40 min	~15% at $\lambda_{0.4-1.0\mu\text{m}}$	Etch rate 0.85 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$
Singh et al. (2001)	NaOH	2 wt% NaOH + 20 vol% IPA	80 °C	45 min	~12% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu\text{m}}$	~20 wt% NaOH SDE
Xi et al. (2004)		2.5 wt% NaOH + 10 wt% CH ₃ COONa	75 °C	35 min	13.5% at $\lambda_{0.24-0.8\mu\text{m}}$	Pre-treatment in HF
Gangopadhyay et al. (2006)		1.8% NaOH + 5% IPA + 4.3% N ₂ H ₂ , H ₂ O	> 90 °C	30 min	~13% in VIS	Batch texturing (25 wafer a batch); IPA not added up to 4 batches

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Reference	Chemical	Optimum Mixture	Temp.	Time	Reflectance	Remark
Vazsonyi et al. (1999)		1.5–4 wt% NaOH + 3 vol% IPA	80 °C	55 min	12.5% at $\lambda_{0.4-0.7\mu\text{m}}$	Etch rate 0.60 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$
You et al. (2001)	TMAH	5 wt.% TMAH	80 °C	30 min	~3% at $\lambda_{0.2-1.2\mu\text{m}}$	Polished. Etching in 2-9 hours did not increase the R
Iencinella et al. (2005)		5 wt.% TMAH	70 °C	40 min	~15% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.1\mu\text{m}}$	Pre-treatment 100 sec dipping in HF
Papet et al. (2006)		2 wt% TMAH + 8 vol% IPA	80 °C	30 min	13% at $\lambda_{0.35-1.1\mu\text{m}}$	Pre-treatment 10 sec dipping in 5% HF
Pakhuruddin et al. (2011)		5 wt.% TMAH	90 °C	10 min	7% at $\lambda_{0.4-1.0\mu\text{m}}$	Pre-treatment RCA with 5 min in 2% HF
Ou et al. (2011)		10 wt% TMAH + 6 vol% IPA	80 °C	25–35 min	~10% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu\text{m}}$	
Kim et al. (2013)		20 wt% TMAH + IPA	80 °C	60 min	11% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.1\mu\text{m}}$	Same R at 30 min with SDE

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Reference	Chemical	Optimum Mixture	Temp.	Time	Reflectance	Remark
Nishimoto & Namba (2000)	Na ₂ CO ₃	20 wt% Na ₂ CO ₃ + NaHCO ₃	95 °C	10 min	11.5% at λ _{0.4-1.0μm}	Etch rate 1.04 μm/min
Sparber et al. (2003)		12 wt% Na ₂ CO ₃ + 1.5 wt% NaHCO ₃	90 °C	40 min	16% at λ _{0.3-1.2μm}	Etch rate 0.55 μm/min
Marrero et al. (2007)		20 wt% Na ₂ CO ₃ + 4 wt% NaHCO ₃	95 °C	20 min	~15% at λ _{0.4-1.0μm}	
Vallejo et al. (2007)		25 wt% Na ₂ CO ₃	95 °C	10 min	12% at λ _{0.4-1.1μm}	Pre-treatment with NaOH SDE and 10% HF
Li et al. (2010)		18 wt% Na ₂ CO ₃	95 °C	25 min	10.7% at λ _{0.3-1.1μm}	Etch rate 0.70 μm/min; using 1mm separation and 1mm ² opening metal grid
Barrio et al. (2013)		25 wt% Na ₂ CO ₃ + 4 wt% NaHCO ₃	90 °C	25 min	15.4% at λ _{0.3-1.25μm}	
Xi et al. (2003)	Na ₃ PO ₄	5% Na ₃ PO ₄ ·12H ₂ O	85 °C	25 min	12.5% at λ _{0.25-0.8μm}	Pre-treatment in HF

Table 5.4 Side effects of texturization onto Si and fabricated solar cell.

	Reason	Explanation
Carrier loss	Increased in surface area	The texture produced increased the surface area which in general increases chances for recombination. Increased in area varies for other textures depends on its size and density.
	Unsaturated dangling bond	The continuity of Si crystal lattice was broken on the textured surface thus exposing unsaturated dangling bond. The bond can be saturated by the hydrogen atom and AR passivation layer.
	Doping concentration	Increases in surface area also affecting the emitter doping concentration which as a factor for higher recombination. Textured surface also leads to uneven p-n junction.
	Ion contamination	Texturization or any post-treatment of Si wafer using KOH/NaOH solution without appropriate cleaning with acidic solution leave the surface of Si with residues of K^+ and Na^+ . Polishing with acid removes the oxides and ions to increase carrier lifetime.
Electrical loss	Poor metal contact	Textured surface after exceeding the optimum size or too rough cause poorer Si-metal contact and although the reflectivity further decreased, resulting to higher R_s . Less sharp pyramids texture lead to uniform metal coverage on front grid lines.
Cell breakdown		Self induced breakdown due to etch pit after selective etching of grain boundaries and dislocation and avalanche breakdown due to spikes in the p-n junction degrades the life of mc-Si solar cell.

Table 5.5 Effect of texturing methods on Si cell performance.

Reference	Method	Texture	Reflectivity	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)	Remark
Gerhards et al. (1997)	Mechanical	mc-Si V-groove		32.70	602.0	77.10	15.20	
Terhaiden & Fath (2003)		c-Si V-groove		38.10	651.0	77.00	19.10	Textured front and rear surface
Fukui et al. (1997)	REI	mc-Si random cones/hillocks	5-10% at $\lambda_{0.45-0.95\mu m}$ (with ARC)	34.10	607.0	76.80	15.90	
Prasad et al. (2010)		mc-Si random cone/peaks	~5% at $\lambda_{0.35-0.8\mu m}$	34.00	600.0	73.00	15.10	
Zhong et al. (2013)		mc-Si random hillocks	~10% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$ (with ARC)	34.00	614.0	76.44	16.00	Acid etching perform better; poor contact
Repo et al. (2013)		c-Si random hillocks	0.7% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.2\mu m}$ (with ARC)	39.30	628.0	75.80	18.70	N-type Si PERL cell
Zielke et al. (2013)	Laser	c-Si smooth crater	~4% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$ (with ARC)	40.30	662.0	74.20	19.80	PERC solar cell

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Reference	Method	Texture	Reflectivity	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)	Remark
Morikawa et al. (2010)	Laser + acid etching	mc-Si honeycomb	~20% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$	37.49	639.0	77.60	18.60	Optimized screen printing and firing
Saito & Kosuge (2007)	Gas etching	c-Si honeycomb or crater-like	~20% at $\lambda_{0.4-0.9\mu m}$	29.60	550.0	77.80	12.70	20 μm feature diameter (large)
Kohata & Saito (2010)		c-Si random texture	17.8% at $\lambda_{0.3-0.9\mu m}$	~37.00	~580.0			
Gangopadhyay et al. (2007)	Acid etching	mc-Si oval pits	15% in VIS	31.74	601.4	74.00	14.12	
Cheng et al. (2011)		mc-Si oval pits	21.41% at $\lambda_{0.3-0.9\mu m}$	17.34	575.0	66.73	13.19	
Sparber et al. (2003)	Alkali etching	c-Si random pyramids	~15% at $\lambda_{0.4-1.0\mu m}$	35.00	614.0	77.50	16.60	
Hayashi et al. (2006)		c-Si random pyramids		33.50	592.0	61.80	12.20	Spherical solar cell

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Reference	Method	Texture	Reflectivity	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)	Remark
Edwards et al. (2008)		c-Si random pyramids	~13% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$	35.00	680.7	74.05	17.64	HIT cell with proper cleaning after etching
Park et al. (2009)		c-Si random pyramids	5.3% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.1\mu m}$ (with ARC)	36.40	524.7	67.40	12.90	No cleaning/acid polishing after texturing
Basu et al. (2013)		mc-Si blunt hillocks		32.26	605.0	76.40	14.96	
Nakamura et al. (2013)		c-Si random pyramids	~10% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$	35.80	629.0	79.90	18.00	
Basu et al. (2013)		c-Si random pyramids	~3% at $\lambda_{0.4-1.0\mu m}$ (with ARC)	36.80	622.4	79.10	18.10	
Marrero et al. (2009)	Alkali + stain etching	c-Si porous pyramids	~7% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.0\mu m}$	30.40	587.4	48.00	8.90	Low quality metallic contact
Chaoui et al. (2013)		c-Si pyramids with Ag particles	~10% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.0\mu m}$ (with ARC)	25.30	585.0	71.90	10.70	Ag (front grid) dissolve in stain etch

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Reference	Method	Texture	Reflectivity	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	η (%)	Remark
Dimitrov & Du (2013)	Alkali + electroless oxidation	c-Si pyramid with nanotexture	< 3% at $\lambda_{0.3-0.9\mu m}$ (with ARC)	35.50	623.0	79.30	17.50	
He et al. (2012)	Electroless etching	Si nanowires		13.60	570.0	71.90	5.60	Si/organic hybrid solar cells
Sardana et al. (2014)	Alkali etching + Ag particles	c-Si pyramid with Ag particles	5.62% at $\lambda_{0.3-1.1\mu m}$	25.62	548.0	45.65	6.420	Overall low performance instead of low R
Chen et al. (2011)	Silica particle deposition	Spherical texture	~10% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$ (with ARC)	37.30	618.0	78.10	18.01	Deposited on c-Si
Yoshinaga et al. (2013)	ZrO ₂ deposition	ZrO ₂ pyramids		40.40	682.0	83.00	22.90	Deposited on c-Si, short λ absorption by ZrO ₂
Wang et al. (1990)	Not disclosed	Regular inverted pyramids	~5% at $\lambda_{0.5-1.0\mu m}$	42.90	696.0	81.00	24.20	PERL solar cell

5.2 SUMMARY

The crystalline silicon have achieve as high as 24% efficiency in earlier days with introduction of passivated emitter and localized (PERL) cell as in Fig. 5.1 by Wang et al. (1990); it was 25 years elapsed since then however nowadays in real industrial use, the cell efficiency mostly still ranged in between 16 to 18% for textured cell either with screen printing or buried contact technology (Fig. 5.2).

Fig. 5.1 Highest bulk Si cell efficiency; PERL design with inverted pyramids texture.

Source: Green et al. 2001

Fig. 5.2 Buried contact cell as an alternative for screen printed contact, with texture.

Source: Green et al. 2001

One of the key architecture of PERL cell is inverted pyramids structure at rear surface incorporated to improve the light trapping scheme as thoroughly discussed in

this writing. Its might only applicable to the lab scale so far as the cell actually require multiple photolithography steps and not easily to be applied on low-cost industrial production (Saga 2010). Multiple findings and alternative techniques which have been reviewed in this study hopefully give an insight and lead a way to cost more simplification, cost effective, and minimize the need of process sophistication in providing desired textured surface on cell surface while maintaining or slightly improve its current light trapping scheme and energy conversion efficiency. Thus, development of new cell architecture will made possible in future; not limited to conventional type but also including thin film and heterojunction silicon cell. Breaking the efficiency barrier 24% or 25% (Green et al. 2001) of silicon based solar cells however in larger view not predominately depends on textured structure and reduction in optical losses that it could offers, but need also to emphasize more on other losses; resistivity losses and minority carrier losses in the cell. Prediction for 80 μ m thick silicon cell in absence of recombination losses is up to 28.8% (Green et al. 2001), included the case of limit Lambertian light trapping. Ultimately, only cell and module manufacturing technologies that could satisfy both high efficiency and low cost will be potential for industrial production in the near future.

This concludes the works done in this dissertation. More than 100 articles were cited to successfully elaborate and provide the essence of R&D on Si solar cell texturization; Table 5.6 and Table 5.7 provided the list of the sources.

Table 5.6 Amount of citation from non-journal article in this dissertation.

No	Source	Amount
1	IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference	8
2	Photovoltaic Specialists Conference	4
3	World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion	2
4	WSEAS International Conference on Renewable Energy Sources	1
5	Proceedings of the SPIE	1
6	International Semiconductor Device Research Symposium	1
7	European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition	1
8	SPIE Newsroom	1
9	Others (public statistics)	2

Table 5.7 Amount of citation from journal with or without impact factor.

No	Journal	Article Amount	Impact Factor
1	Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells	28	5.337
2	Applied Surface Science	7	2.711
3	Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications	6	7.584
4	Solar Energy	5	3.469
5	IEEE Transaction on Electron Devices	4	2.358 (2013)
6	Sensor and Actuators A	4	1.903
7	Journal of Applied Physics	3	2.183
8	Applied Physics Letters	3	3.515 (2013)
9	Energy Procedia	3	-
10	IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics	2	3.000 (2013)
11	Journal of the Electrochemical Society	2	3.266
12	Journal of the Korean Physical Society	2	-
13	Materials Science Forum	2	-
14	Materials Science and Engineering B	1	2.169
15	Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing	1	1.995
16	Journal of the European Ceramic Society	1	2.947
17	Journal of Achievements in Materials and Manufacturing Engineering	1	-
18	Rare Metals	1	0.086 (2013)
19	Physica Status Solidi C	1	-
20	Current Applied Physics	1	2.212
21	Thin Solid Films	1	1.759
22	Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids	1	1.766
23	Physics of Plasmas	1	2.142
24	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	1	5.901
25	Optoelectronics and Advanced Materials-rapid Communications	1	0.394
26	NPG Asia Mater	1	10.118
27	Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics	1	1.966 (2013)
28	Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering	1	1.725 (2013)
29	Renewable Energy	1	3.476
30	Optics Express	1	3.488
31	Semiconductor Science and Technology	1	2.206 (2013)

The reason why articles from non-journal and no/low impact factor managed to be included in the list is because of containing some useful information/argument.

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